

Optimisation Of Light Collection In Liquid Argon Detectors And Modelling Pulse Shape Discrimination For Dark Matter Searches

By

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Thesis

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Abstract

The Dark Matter hypothesis has emerged as the favoured explanation for the otherwise unexplained motion of celestial bodies at galactic scales and beyond. It proposes the existence of a form of matter that interacts with ordinary matter primarily through gravity. Though no credible detection of Weakly Interacting Massive Particles (WIMPs)—the leading dark matter candidate—has yet been made, the parameter space for WIMPs is steadily shrinking. To further constrain this space, more sensitive detectors must be developed, which presents several technological challenges. One promising approach for direct WIMP detection is the use of liquid argon (LAr) as a target material.

Liquid argon-based dark matter detectors exploit the scintillation properties of liquid argon for suppressing the background generated by the beta decay of ^{39}Ar . In order to accurately evaluate the expected rate of background events with uncertainty, a robust background model that can be tuned to the detector data and reliably extrapolated orders of magnitude beyond the available background statistics, is needed. This thesis will present the validation and further development of a physics-driven simulation to model the complete detection process from scintillation to light detection. Since high statistics simulations are computationally expensive, the model has been implemented in Python using PyTorch framework, which significantly reduces the computation time using parallel processing on GPU(s). On a single GPU, the PyTorch implementation is two orders of magnitude faster than the ROOT implementation.

A WIMP-argon nucleus collision would produce scintillation light in the vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) regime, where conventional photosensors have low efficiency. To enhance detection efficiency, detector internal surfaces can be coated with wavelength-shifting (WLS) materials to down-shift the VUV photons to the visible spectrum. Applying Tetraphenyl butadiene (TPB), the most common WLS in use for LAr, over the large surface areas of next-generation detectors with vacuum evaporation is energy and labour inefficient and calls for more scalable approaches. For this reason, polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) will be used as wavelength shifter in the DarkSide-20k veto detectors, currently under construction. For the purpose of quality assurance of PEN, multiple samples needs to be tested at cryogenic temperatures. To this end, a new Argon Gas Setup (ArGSet) has been recently commissioned for measuring the wavelength-shifting efficiency of PEN with the argon scintillation. This thesis will discuss the calibration of this setup and present results of the first PEN measurement. It will also present room temperature fluorescence measurements, indicating its satisfactory and uniform performance across the axial length of the roll of PEN procured to be used in the veto of the DarkSide-20k detector.

Finally, this thesis presents an analytic tool developed for estimation of the light yield of liquid argon detectors and its cross-validation with Monte Carlo simulations and experimental data. It also discusses invaluable insights the analytic tool provides for the design of the future large-scale detectors.

Streszczenie

Hipoteza ciemnej materii stała się preferowanym wyjaśnieniem anomalii w ruchu ciał niebieskich w skali galaktycznej i poza nią. Proponuje ona istnienie formy materii, która oddziałuje ze zwykłą materią głównie poprzez grawitację. Chociaż nie dokonano jeszcze w sposób niezbity odkrycia słabo oddziałujących masywnych cząstek (WIMP) - głównego kandydata na ciemną materię - przestrzeń parametrów dostępnych WIMP-om stale się kurczy. Aby jeszcze bardziej ograniczyć tę przestrzeń, należy opracować bardziej czułe detektory, z czym wiąże się kilka wyzwań technologicznych. Jednym z obiecujących podejść do bezpośredniego wykrywania WIMP-ów jest wykorzystanie ciekłego argonu jako tarczy.

Detektory ciemnej materii oparte na ciekłym argonie wykorzystują właściwości scyntylacyjne ciekłego argonu do tłumienia tła generowanego przez rozpady beta ^{39}Ar . Aby dokładnie oszacować oczekiwaną częstość zdarzeń tła i jej niepewność, potrzebny jest solidny model tła, który można dostroić do danych detektora i wiarygodnie ekstrapolować rzędy wielkości poza dostępne statystyki zdarzeń tła. W niniejszej rozprawie przedstawiono walidację i dalszy rozwój modelu symulacyjnego opartego na procesach fizycznych, w celu modelowania pełnego procesu detekcji od scyntylacji do detekcji światła. Ponieważ symulacje o wysokiej statystyce są kosztowne obliczeniowo, model został zaimplementowany w Pythonie przy użyciu bibliotek PyTorch, który znacznie skraca czas obliczeń dzięki użyciu przetwarzania równoległego na procesorach graficznych. Na pojedynczym procesorze graficznym implementacja PyTorch jest o dwa rzędy wielkości szybsza niż jedno-procesorowa implementacja oparta na bibliotekach ROOT.

Zderzenie jądra WIMP z argonem wytwarza światło scyntylacyjne z zakresu próżniowego ultrafioletu (VUV). Jednak konwencjonalne fotosensory mają w tym reżimie niską wydajność. Aby zwiększyć wydajność detekcji, wewnętrzne powierzchnie detektorów są pokrywane materiałami przesuwanymi widmo (wavelength shifter), aby zamienić fotony VUV w widzialne. Produkcja powłok z tych materiałów na dużych powierzchniach detektorów nowej generacji przy pomocy tradycyjnej metody naporowania próżniowego jest nieefektywna i wymaga dużych nakładów energii, siły roboczej i czasu, co motywuje nowe bardziej skalowalne podejścia, będące kolejnym elementem niniejszej pracy doktorskiej.

Z tego powodu polimerowa folia z naftalanu polietylenu (PEN) będzie użyta jako przesuwnik widma w detektorze weta DarkSide-20k, który jest obecnie w budowie. W celu sprawdzenia odpowiedniej jakości PEN konieczne było przetestowanie wielu próbek w warunkach kriogenicznych. W tym celu niedawno uruchomione zostało nowe stanowisko badawcze Argon Gas Setup (ArGSet) do pomiaru wydajności przesuwania widma przez PEN, przy wzbudzeniu za pomocą scyntylacji gazowego argonu. W niniejszej rozprawie omówiona jest kalibracja tego zestawu i przedstawione są wyniki pierwszego pomiaru PEN. Przedstawione są również pomiary fluorescencji w temperaturze pokojowej, wskazujące na jego zadowalającą i jednorodną wydajność na całej długości osiowej szpuli PEN zakupionej do wykorzystania w wiecie detektora DarkSide-20k.

Wreszcie, niniejsza rozprawa przedstawia narzędzie analityczne opracowane do

szacowania wydajności zbierania światła w detektorach ciekło-argonowych i jego porównanie z symulacjami Monte Carlo i danymi eksperymentalnymi. Omówiono są również uzyskane dzięki niemu wnioski, przydatne przy projektowaniu przyszłych detektorów wielkoskalowych.

Dedicated to Maa

I am very proud to dedicate this thesis to my mother and sister, for they taught me when none would.

Not knowing the scope of your own ignorance is part of the human condition. The problem with it is we see it in other people, and we don't see it in ourselves. The first rule of the Dunning–Kruger club is you don't know you're a member of the Dunning–Kruger club.

– David Dunning

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to Captain Kirk, although I don't know his real name or if he was even the captain of KLM flight KL872. On January 9, 2021, the day I was scheduled to travel from Delhi to Warsaw via Amsterdam to start my PhD at CAMK, I wasn't feeling well. For the past two days, I had witnessed a sudden increase in my visits to the market, and now I was exhausted. I had booked seats with extra legroom, and I was hoping for a comfortable flight. It is no secret that I do not like travelling, but I didn't think it was anything more than pre-flight jitters. However, the moment I set foot inside the plane, I had a feeling my dinner wouldn't stay down for long. Before I could vomit all over myself, I grabbed a sick bag just in time to empty the contents of my stomach.

The family seated next to me must have been mortified. I vaguely recall the look of horror in the stewardess's eyes. I don't know what she was planning to say, but the moment she saw me, she rushed toward the cockpit. You see, in early 2021, COVID-19 was still raging across the globe. Travel regulations were strict, and airlines reserved the right to deny boarding even for mild symptoms of illness. I briefly considered getting off the plane—after all, the ticket had only cost €1,000—but something in me hesitated.

The stewardess soon returned with an older gentleman wearing a uniform different from the cabin crew. He must have been the captain or a senior officer. He asked if I was feeling okay and inquired whether I had eaten something unusual. When I mentioned that I might have eaten something questionable, he reassured me, saying it was probably just food poisoning. He then gave me a choice: I could disembark or continue the journey.

I don't remember my exact thought process, but I recall feeling that if I got off the plane, I wouldn't try again. Enough had transpired between my interview and boarding this flight that I felt I no longer had the strength for another attempt. I told the gentleman—whom I now fondly call Captain Kirk—that I wanted to stay on the flight. And that was that.

The stewardess moved me to the back of the plane, where there was an empty row, ensuring I wouldn't disturb anyone. The rest of the flight was uneventful. In the following four years, there were two more moments when the fate of my PhD hung in the balance. While I won't go into the details, as you can guess, I didn't quit.

All in all, if Captain Kirk hadn't given me that choice, leaving the PhD program wouldn't have felt like my decision. I likely would have resigned myself to thinking, *this is life*, and moved on. I would probably have always wondered what might have been. *I can't help but hope there's a version of me in the multiverse who made a different choice.* In the end, good or bad, it was my decision and I own it.

Preface

This thesis is the culmination of the work I performed over the past four years as part of my doctoral education at the Nicolaus Copernicus Astronomical Center.

The guiding principle of the writing style of this thesis has been the concise, clear, and exact use of words. However, being succinct is more important than being precise. Therefore, on occasion, I deviate from precise language to present the content in a more pedagogical manner.

In instances where I need to define special terms or use specific terminology, I place them inside green terminology boxes. Another type of box found throughout this thesis is the grey box. I use grey boxes to discuss topics that, while not strictly necessary for understanding the thesis content, enrich the discussion. These discussions might be useful for forming a more holistic view of the broader topic. The idea of these grey boxes is inspired by the ‘Do You Know’ boxes in textbooks published by the National Council of Educational Research and Training.

The thesis is organized into seven chapters:

Chapter 1 introduces the concept of dark matter, its significance, and detection schemes.

Chapter 2 delves into the foundational concepts of liquid argon radiation detectors, setting the stage for the subsequent investigations.

Chapter 3 presents a discussion on Pulse Shape Discrimination as employed in liquid argon experiments for direct detection of dark matter search.

Chapter 4 provides a detailed description of an analytic approach for estimation of light yield of liquid argon detectors.

Chapters 5 and 6 share the theme of characterizing wavelength shifters for use in liquid argon detectors.

Finally, Chapter 7 concludes the thesis with a comprehensive summary of the findings, their implications, and potential directions for future work.

Sarthak Choudhary

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List of Symbols

χ^2/ν	Reduced chi-square
ϵ_{sPE}	Standard deviation in the mean sPE charge
Λ	Cosmological Constant
λ_{abs}	interaction length of absorption
λ_{eff}	effective interaction length
λ_R	interaction length of Rayleigh scattering
\overline{Q}_{sPE}	Mean sPE charge
$G(\mu, \sigma)$	Gaussian function with stand deviation σ and mean μ
a_0	Universal constant introduced by MOND
c	speed of light in vacuum
F_{prompt}	PSD parameter
f_{sen}	Fraction of surface area covered with Photosensors
FF_{sys}	Fill Factor: the fraction of active area on the light detecting surface of the photosensor
h	Planck's constant
L_{char}	Characteristic Length
nPE	number of Photo-Electrons
PSP_{VUV}	Photon Survival Probability of VUV photons
Q_{VUV}	Q factor for VUV regime

List of Acronyms

2PAC 2 Parallel Argon Chambers

ArGSet Argon Gas Setup

AMELY Analytic Model for Estimation of Light Yield

ARC Anti-Reflection Coating

AR-MA Auto-Recursive Moving-Average

ALP Axion-like particle

CDM Cold Dark Matter

CMB Cosmic Microwave Background

COM Center of Mass

DAQ Data Acquisition system

DWArF DarkWave Argon Facility

IS Integrating Sphere

HV High Voltage

LArS Liquid Argon Setup

LCE Light Collection Efficiency

LHC Large Hadron Collider

LMC Large Magellanic Cloud

LY Light Yield

MC Monte Carlo

MA Moving Average

MACHO MAssive Compact Halo Object

MOND Modified Newtonian Dynamics

- OV** Over-Voltage
- PDE** Photon Detection Efficiency
- PDP** Photon Detection Probability
- PDU** photodetector units
- PE** Photo-Electron
- PEN** Polyethylene Naphthalate
- PMMA** polymethyl methacrylate
- PMT** Photomultiplier Tubes
- PSD** Pulse Shape Discrimination
- PSP** Photon Survival Probability
- pTP** p-Terphenyl
- RMS** Root Mean Square
- RT** Room Temperature
- SiPM** Silicon PhotoMultiplier
- SNR** Signal to Noise Ratio
- SPAD** Single-photon Avalanche Diode
- sPE** single Photo-Electron
- SY** Scintillation Yield
- TPB** Tetraphenyl Butadiene
- TPC** Time Projection Chamber
- UZH** University of Zurich
- VUV** Vacuum Ultraviolet
- WIMP** Weakly Interacting Massive Particle
- WLS** Wavelength Shifter
- WLSE** Wavelength Shifting Efficiency
- WLSR** Wavelength Shifting Reflector

Chapter 1

Dark Matter

This thesis in its entirety is dedicated to advancement of liquid argon detectors for direct detection of dark matter. While this chapter will present the primary motivation behind the search for dark matter, the chapter 2 will give a brief overview of liquid argon detectors. The rest of the thesis will focus on specific aspects of liquid argon dark matter detectors where I have made direct contributions.

It is not the intent of this chapter to be a primer on dark matter phenomenology, but to present the topic in a brief, yet concise manner. I will introduce the missing matter problem for which dark matter was first invoked, then touch upon the paradigm of cold dark matter, followed by a discussion on suitable candidates for dark matter particles. But let us, first, try to understand what is meant by dark matter.

1.1 Introduction

Dark matter is any hypothetical form of matter invoked to explain certain discrepancies in astronomical observations described in the section 1.2.

Firstly, I make a distinction between two different terms I use in this chapter, namely, the astronomical dark matter and the particle dark matter.

The problem of missing matter, in its simplest form, is that the motion of celestial matter in systems of the scale of galaxy and larger does not seem to follow the Newtonian mechanics (see subsections 1.2.1 and 1.2.2). The deviations can, however, be explained by invoking the presence of dark matter. The reasoning goes that this additional mass could be provided by a difficult-to-observe form of matter, which I would refer to as the **astronomical dark matter**. The astronomical dark matter, could be very different things: from relatively small scale celestial bodies, e.g., black holes, neutron stars, giant gas planets, to a diffuse yet undiscovered form of matter that does not interact with electromagnetic radiation.

This entirely new form of non-luminous matter, which could provide this additional mass without contributing to the total luminosity of the galaxy, is also of interest to particle physics, and I will refer to this as **particle dark matter** [1].

The inability of Standard Model [2] to fully unify the weak, strong, and electromagnetic interactions [3], or provide a solution to the strong CP problem [4] have

propelled physicists to look for a more general extension of the Standard Model, such as supersymmetry theories [5]. These theories, in turn, propose new particles, some of these hypothetical particles fulfil all criteria required for a good dark matter candidate.

Properties of ideal dark matter candidates :

1. Does not emit or absorb light
2. It has mass
3. Not hot, i.e., moving slow compared to speed of light
4. It should be stable

1.2 Evidence for Dark Matter

The astronomical observations which remain unreconcilable under Newtonian mechanics without extra mass are described in this section. It is worth noting that these discrepancies arise only while investigating structures of the size of a galaxy or larger. While some of these observations might be explained away without invoking dark matter, it is currently not considered possible to explain all of these with a single theory other than particle dark matter.

1.2.1 Galactic Rotation Curves

Vera Rubin and Kent Ford published a study with galactic rotation curves in the year 1970 [6]. A galactic rotation curve is a plot of velocity of stars of a galaxy as a function of their distance from the centre of the galaxy (see figure 1.1). Under the assumption of dynamic stability, one would expect the velocity of disk stars to decrease with distance on the account of inverse square nature of Newtonian gravitational pull, which would be acting as the centripetal force. Using the Doppler shift in visible wavelengths, they measured the stellar velocities for the galaxy M31. And as it turns out, the rotation curves which they made tend to plateau rather than fall with distance. In a separate study published few months later that year, KC Freeman showed that the maximum velocity is at much larger radii than expected [7]. Later studies [8], confirmed this trend to be a rather common feature of galaxy dynamics.

The discovery of flat rotation curves was one of the two groundbreaking works that would later become crucial evidence for in favour of the dark matter hypothesis [9], the other being measurement of the mass of the Coma cluster.

Figure 1.1: Rotation curve of the spiral galaxy Messier 33 (Triangulum). The image also shows the velocity of gas clouds, which are measured using the Doppler shift in 21 cm neutral hydrogen line. Image credit: Mario De Leo [10], licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0. Based on data from [11].

Box: Image Tube Spectrograph

It was Kent Ford's invention of the Image Tube Spectrograph [12] that made it possible to measure the spectra of those stars at high resolution. Once the light had been dispersed into its component wavelengths, the photocathode of the image tube would convert it into Photo-Electrons and then these Photo-Electrons would be accelerated and projected onto a phosphorescent screen. This provided the signal amplification need for measurements of faint signals from edges of the galaxy, which would not have been possible with a photoplate.

Box: Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND)

While it is true that the galactic rotation curves were crucial evidence in support of dark matter in the 1970s, right when the interest in dark matter was starting to pick up, one should not assume that this observation alone is sufficient evidence for the existence of dark matter today. With the rise of Modified Newtonian Dynamics [13], rotation curves ceased to be sufficient evidence. Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND) was proposed by physicist Mordehai Milgrom as an alternative approach to explain these rotation curves. The best, most concise way to describe MOND is probably the one by Ethan Siegel [14] who says,

“What MOND hypothesized was fascinating: that very far from the centers of galaxies, on scales of thousands of light-years or more, the predicted accelerations of stars around their galactic centers would be extremely small, but they’re being pulled by a system, overall, of tremendously substantial (normal matter) mass. If the acceleration caused by that central mass drops below a critical value — a new hypothesized constant of nature — then the acceleration isn’t determined by the gravitational force (or curvature of space) caused by the dominating mass, but rather reverts to that minimal value.”

According to MOND, the force F_N experienced by an object of mass m under a field that produces an acceleration a can be written as:

$$F_N = m\mu\left(\frac{a}{a_0}\right)a \quad (1.1)$$

where, $\mu(x)$ is an interpolating function defined in MOND and a_0 is a new universal constant, such that,

$$\mu(x) \rightarrow 1 \text{ for } x \gg 1 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\mu(x) \rightarrow x \text{ for } x \ll 1 \quad (1.3)$$

For objects far from the galaxy centre where gravitational acceleration is small,

$$\mu\left(\frac{a}{a_0}\right) = \frac{a}{a_0} \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_N = m\left(\frac{a^2}{a_0}\right) \quad (1.5)$$

Since, F_N provides the centripetal force,

$$F_{Gravitational} = F_{centripetal} \quad (1.6)$$

$$F_{Gravitational} = F_N \quad (1.7)$$

Under the assumption of circular orbits, the radial component of velocity of an object at a distance of r from the galaxy centre can be written as

$$a = \frac{v^2}{r} \quad (1.8)$$

$$\frac{GMm}{r^2} = m \frac{\left(\frac{v^2}{r}\right)^2}{a_0} \quad (1.9)$$

$$v^4 = GMa_0 \quad (1.10)$$

The value of a_0 is determined empirically to be $a_0 = (1.27 \pm 0.30) \times 10^{-10} \text{ m/s}^2$ [15].

Thus, the velocity becomes independent of distance from centre of galaxy for small acceleration fields under Milgrom paradigm. MOND was introduced to explain the galactic rotation curves, and it does that extremely well. Consider this, while the dark matter halo models, e.g., Navarro–Frenk–White profile [16], varies from halo to halo, a_0 is constant universally. However, MOND is not enough to explain several other anomalous observations, e.g, the masses of galaxy clusters, or anisotropies in Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB).

At this point, I would bring the discussion on MOND to a conclusion, as I believe I have provided sufficient material for readers to assess the state of affairs as to where we are with dark matter and MOND to an extent suitable for this thesis. However, I should mention a very common misconception which a lot of people seem to have regarding MOND, that it is a theory of modified gravity, which is not true. MOND is a framework of theories for modification of Newton’s second law of motion, though it is possible to interpret it as modification of Newton’s law of gravitation, it is also possible to interpret it as modification of inertia [17]. For the case of modification of inertia, we can wonder whether MOND might apply to all other interactions as well [18].

1.2.2 Masses of Galaxy Clusters

Astrophysicist Fritz Zwicky published a study [19, 20] demonstrating application of the virial theorem to determine mass of the Coma cluster (see figure 1.2). Another method of calculating the mass of a cluster is to calculate the mass of the individual galaxies from the mass–luminosity relation for galaxies and adding up the masses of all galaxies. Zwicky compared the masses calculated using the two methods. His estimates using virial theorem were 400 times higher than the visible mass. He postulated that one of the reasons for this discrepancy could be that unseen matter must be present in the system. He coined the term ‘dunkle Materie’ to refer to this missing matter. Although his mass estimates were significantly off due to the limitations of observational techniques of the time, Zwicky’s use of virial theorem for determining the mass of the cluster was groundbreaking nonetheless. Over the decades, as the technology improved, the masses determined using virial theorem have improved, but they are still much higher than those determined using the luminosity [21, 22].

Figure 1.2: Coma cluster

1.2.3 Colliding Galaxy Clusters: The Case of the Bullet Cluster

The Bullet Cluster (1E 0657-56) consists of two colliding galaxy clusters. The Bullet Cluster is actually the smaller bullet shaped subcluster, which is moving away from the larger one (see figure 1.3). The figure 1.3b shows that the X-ray emitting intergalactic gas (bright-coloured regions) has lagged, while the majority of the colliding clusters have moved ahead (green contours) as if they didn't participate in the collision. This is not just an evidence for dark matter, but the evidence that the non-baryonic matter is the dominant constituent of this system [23].

1.2.4 Cosmology

At present, perhaps, the strongest argument in favour of non-baryonic dark matter is that the standard model of cosmology needs it. The standard model of cosmology, also known as, the Λ CDM model, is a model in the paradigm of Big Bang Theory. The model has three components:

1. Λ : Λ parameter, also known as the cosmological constant, was introduced to constraint the total mass of an expanding Universe and keeps the Universe flat at large scale. It is associated with an even less understood entity, dark energy.
2. Cold Dark Matter: Cold means dark matter is moving slowly compared to speed of light. Cold Dark Matter (CDM) is required to allow formation of galaxies and the large scale structures observed in our Universe.
3. ordinary matter: entire Standard Model, i.e., baryons, leptons, bosons mediating the four fundamental Standard Model forces, and the Higgs boson.

This theory has been exceptionally successful in explaining many observations [25]:

(a) Composite image of the Bullet Cluster. The background displays visible light captured by the Magellan and Hubble Space Telescopes. The pink overlay highlights X-ray emissions from the colliding clusters, observed by the Chandra X-ray Telescope, while the blue overlay represents the clusters' mass distribution, derived from gravitational lensing effects. Image credit: [24]

(b) Image of the Bullet Cluster captured by the Chandra X-ray Observatory. The X-ray brightness of the gas is represented using yellow, red, and blue colours. The distribution of gravitating mass, determined through weak lensing reconstruction, is depicted with green contours. Image taken from Ref. [23].

Figure 1.3: Different representations of Bullet Cluster to infer presence of non-baryonic dark matter

Figure 1.4: Graph showing the angular anisotropy of the square of the CMB temperature fluctuation as a function of multipole moments. The black dots with red error bars represent data from the Planck satellite observations, while the green curve depicts the theoretical model. An inset oval displays the Planck all-sky map of CMB intensity fluctuations. Image credit: [29]

While investigating the galactic evolution, cosmologist Jim Peebles and astronomer Jeremiah Ostriker realised that in the numerical simulations, galaxies were not forming the spiral arms observed for many galaxies. They solved this problem by adding a halo of dark matter around the galaxies.

Peebles also showed that the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) would have a temperature variation of about 5 parts in 10^5 , which would later be verified by precision measurement of CMB by several experiments [26].

A key postulate of this theory is that the large scale structures in the Universe are formed as a result of very small perturbations in the matter distributions of the Universe during its infancy, and the gravitational clustering causes these structures to grow. The radiation emitted from the early Universe is now observable as CMB. This CMB contains an imprint of the state of the Universe at that time. It has been shown that by including the information from CMB in the numerical simulations, one can get correct distribution of galaxies using the Λ CDM model [27].

Finally, figure 1.4 shows the theoretical fits to the angular power spectrum of CMB temperature anisotropies. This way, information about the spacetime geometry and the baryon density can be extracted from CMB. The temperature fluctuations are expanded in spherical harmonics to compute the temperature angular power spectrum. The inflation predicts anisotropy to be a Gaussian random field [28].

1.3 Dark Matter candidates

1.3.1 MACHO

Following the discussion in subsections 1.2.1 and 1.2.2, one might come to wonder, perhaps, the missing matter can be present in the form of celestial bodies that are massive enough to constitute enough mass but faint enough to escape observation with astronomical telescopes. This would be a more natural hypothesis than assuming invisible matter spread across the galaxy. Consider this: I have referenced the works of Fritz Zwicky and KC Freeman in their respective subsections. Though they suspected unaccounted matter could be responsible for the observed deviations from Newtonian mechanics, they did not, specifically, say that the matter needs to be of exotic nature, that hypothesis came later.

From the very beginning, it was realized that a population of faint, difficult-to-detect celestial bodies, or MAAssive Compact Halo Object (**MACHO**) as they would come to be known, lurking at the edges of the galaxies could be the astronomical dark matter everybody was looking for. As is the norm in academia, this led to a raging debate whether astronomical dark matter indeed consisted of these MACHOs or some undiscovered exotic form of matter. A number of candidates including brown dwarfs ($\leq 0.08 M_{\odot}$), jupiters ($\approx 0.001 M_{\odot}$), and black holes ($\approx 100 M_{\odot}$) are possible candidates for MACHOs [30].

But the question was how does one go about finding a MACHO? The astrophysicist Bohdan Paczyński had an idea. He suggested that such halo object could be detected indirectly by observing its microlensing effect on another star's light [31]. When a massive object passes through the line of sight between a star and an observer, the object's gravitational field would bend the light's path, focusing the light towards the observer, which would cause an apparent brightening of the star. This is known as microlensing effect. One of the parameters that determine the duration of this apparent brightening is the mass of the halo object, the heavier the object, the longer will be the duration of brightening.

Thus was born the MACHO project [32], aimed at search for microlensing events by observing millions of stars of the Large Magellanic Cloud (**LMC**). They succeeded at observing microlensing effect, but the observed number of microlensing events fell short of expectations. Thus, they concluded that the MACHO can not constitute 100% of dark matter halo mass in the Milky Way [33]. EROS, another microlensing survey aimed at LMC, also ruled out MACHOs as the major constituent of dark matter halo in our galaxy [34].

1.3.2 WIMP

Weakly Interacting Massive Particle (**WIMP**) are perhaps the best known and most sought after particle dark matter candidates. The entire discussion in this thesis is centred on WIMP detection. The WIMP refers to a class of hypothetical particles which primarily interact via weak force. They are expected to have mass in range from $50 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ to few TeV/c^2 [35].

What makes WIMP a viable candidate for dark matter search:

1. WIMP model can achieve the correct relic abundance required in the early Universe [35].
2. Some extensions to Standard Model end up with particles with similar properties as WIMPs. WIMP could be the lightest supersymmetric particle (LSP) predicted by supersymmetry theories [5].
3. Although weakly, WIMP can interact with the baryonic matter, which makes them difficult to detect, yet detectable, at least in a fraction of the parameter space.

Detection schemes

1. **Indirect detection:** these particles can annihilate when their density reaches a critical value, e.g., at the galactic centre. Experiments such as AMS-02 [36] look for these annihilation signals.
2. **Production at colliders:** the idea behind WIMP searches at colliders is that if WIMP do exist, perhaps, they can be produced in particle colliders such as the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) [37]. While the radiation detectors at LHC can not detect these WIMPs directly, they can still infer the WIMP production, e.g., from the signature of missing momentum [38].
3. **Direct detection:** Highly sensitive underground experiments have been developed to detect the signature of WIMPs scattering off ordinary matter, e.g., DEAP-3600 [39], LUX-ZEPLIN [40], SuperCDMS [41]. Chapter 2 will present a brief discussion on liquid argon detectors for the direct dark matter searches.

The figure 1.5 shows a summary of detection schemes employed:

Figure 1.5: Detection schemes for WIMP dark matter.

1.3.3 Axion and Axion-like particles

Another category of candidates for particle dark matter is axions and Axion-like particle (ALP). The emergence of axions in theoretical particle physics is a natural consequence of Peccei-Quinn mechanism, proposed to solve the strong CP problem by explaining the apparent conservation of CP symmetry in strong interactions [42]. ALPs can be thought of as a generic version of axions. While axions are specifically linked to the strong CP problem, ALPs are invoked to solve a variety of problem, including that of providing non-baryonic dark matter.

Mass range: 10^{-5} eV/c² to 1 eV/c²

Detection scheme: signature of conversion to photons under strong electromagnetic field [43].

1.3.4 Sterile Neutrino

Sterile neutrino is a hypothetical neutrino with no coupling to weak interactions [44]. This means that the sterile neutrino are left only with gravitational interaction, through which they can interact with ordinary matter. Since elementary particles are very light, gravitational interaction becomes significant only for a large number of particles. This makes it an excellent candidate for dark matter.

But then the problem is how does one search for sterile neutrino if it does not interact via any interaction. Since it is expected that sterile neutrino will participate in mass oscillations like other neutrinos, deficiency in observed number of a particular flavour of neutrino would hint at the neutrinos oscillations involving sterile neutrino. They could explain anomalies observed in many neutrino experiments (e.g., the LSND [45] and MiniBooNE [46] experiments).

Importantly, however, sterile neutrinos would be an example of hot dark matter. This has implications for the galactic dark matter halo substructures, and results in a smaller number of sub-halos, predicted by large-scale N-body simulations of the Universe evolution, than for cold dark matter. The cold dark matter scenario is more consistent with the observations, even if still leaving some room for the intermediate 'warm' dark matter case.

Subtypes: It is suspected that there might be several flavours of sterile neutrino [47].

Mass range: 1 eV/c² to 15 GeV/c² [48]

Detection scheme: anomalies in neutrino flavour oscillations [49].

Chapter 2

Liquid Argon Radiation Detectors

Liquid argon detectors present a promising approach for efficient detection of rare events, e.g., WIMP-nucleon scattering. This chapter is going to present a brief overview of liquid argon radiation detectors employed for rare event searches, including usual backgrounds considered for dark matter searches, and photon detection systems.

2.1 Introduction

What is the challenge of direct detection of WIMPs?

It is that the WIMPs, if they exist, are expected to have very small interaction cross-sections. I have compiled the table 2.1 to impress upon the readers just how the expected WIMP interaction cross-sections compare to cross-sections of other particle interactions.

These extremely small cross-sections translate to very low value of expected event rate (see figure 2.1). Since the expected event rate is extremely low, noise and background become considerably dominant. This results into very stringent requirements on detector technology employed. The detector material is assayed extensively to ensure radio purity standards are met for achieving design sensitivity to WIMP interactions. Note that such experiments employ some background rejection technique to further suppress the effect of background. Chapter 3 will further add to the topic of background rejection in liquid argon experiments with the aid of a technique known as Pulse Shape Discrimination.

Target	Incident Particle	Energy of the incident particle [MeV/c ²]	cross-section [barns]	Notes	Sources
Nucleon	WIMP	10 ⁵	$\sim 10^{-20}$ to 10^{-24}	Representative cross-section typical of recent WIMP searches.	[39, 50]
Ar (Gas)	Proton	1.0	≈ 0.07	Elastic scattering cross-section	[51]
Proton	Neutron	150.9	0.0512 ± 0.001	Total interaction cross-section.	[52]
Ar (Gas)	Neutron	6	2.17 ± 0.13	Elastic scattering cross-section.	[53]
Ar (Liquid)	Neutron	674 to 900	0.83 ± 0.32	Total interaction cross-section.	[54]
Ar (Liquid)	Muon neutrino	~ 800 MeV	$\sim 10^{-14}$	Charged current interaction cross-section	[55]

Table 2.1: Typical interaction cross-sections [barns].

Consider this: DEAP-3600, which is a 3.3-tonne liquid argon detector, has about 5×10^{28} argon atoms. The expected WIMP interaction rate is less than 10 events per tonne-year, equating to less than 3 events per month. Thus, we can safely assume it is highly unlikely to observe more than 1 WIMP event at any given moment. Therefore, we need to design a radiation detection system capable of detecting WIMP scattering off one out of $\approx 5 \times 10^{28}$ argon atoms.

2.2 WIMP event rate and direct detection sensitivity

The direct detection event rate is given as follows [56]:

$$R (\text{events/kg/yr}) = \langle \Phi_\chi \cdot \sigma_{\chi N} \rangle \cdot \frac{N_0}{A} \quad (2.1)$$

where,

Φ_χ = WIMP Flux

$\sigma_{\chi N}$ = WIMP-Nucleus Scattering cross-section

N_0 = Avogadro's number

A = Atomic mass of target nuclei in atomic mass units

N_0/A = Number of target nuclei

Then, the differential event rate can be written as:

$$\frac{dR}{dE_R} = \frac{N_0}{A} \int_0^\infty \frac{d\sigma(E_R, v_\chi)}{dE_R} \frac{d\Phi_\chi(v_\chi)}{dv_\chi} dv_\chi \quad (2.2)$$

where,

v_χ = velocity of WIMP particle

$\frac{d\sigma(E_R, v_\chi)}{dE_R}$ = the differential cross-section for dark matter-nucleus scattering

For the spin independent case, the differential cross-section for dark matter-nucleus scattering can be written as:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dE_R} = \frac{m_N}{2\mu_{\chi N}^2 v_\chi^2} \sigma_0 F^2(E_R) \quad (2.3)$$

where:

m_N = the nuclear mass

$\mu_{\chi N} = \frac{m_\chi m_N}{m_\chi + m_N}$ = reduced mass of the dark matter-nucleus system

σ_0 = zero-momentum transfer dark matter-nucleus cross-section

$F(E_R)$ = nuclear form factor

Generally, the energy spectrum of WIMP-induced nuclear recoils is steeply and nearly exponentially falling with increasing recoil energy. Heavier elements have higher expected WIMP event rate, as the coherent elastic scattering cross-section scales with the square of the atomic mass, A^2 . The expected event rate for different elements is shown in the figure 2.1. However, the nuclear form-factor, results in suppression and ‘dips’ in the differential cross-section for characteristic recoil energies, reflecting the loss of coherence, which below 100 keV is more prominent for heavier elements.

Figure 2.1: Differential event rate for the direct detection of a $100 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ WIMP with a cross-section of 10^{-45} cm^2 using different materials as targets, including tungsten (green), xenon (black), iodine (magenta), germanium (red), argon (blue), and sodium (grey). Ref [56]

The above recoil energy spectra allows one to translate the absence of candidate WIMP events in a dark matter detector into an upper limit on the WIMP-nucleon scattering cross-section as a function of the WIMP mass. The current leading exclusion limits are shown in figure 2.2, together with the so-called neutrino fog, i.e., the sensitivity at which neutrinos will become an irreducible background for direct WIMP searches, practically bringing them to an end.

It is interesting to note that detectors based on liquid xenon (LZ, XENONnT and PandaX) and liquid argon (DarkSide-50) are currently dominating the field, for reasons to be explained in the next subsection. Currently, liquid Xe has the edge

Figure 2.2: Current leading experimental upper limits on the spin-independent WIMP-nucleon scattering. The ‘neutrino floor’ is shown in yellow. From Ref [57].

over liquid Ar in searches for heavier-mass WIMPs, mainly due to the aforementioned A^2 cross-section enhancement. Further scale-up of LXe detectors is however limited by the dramatically higher cost of xenon; liquid Ar, on the other hand, in addition to better scalability, offers more powerful handles against backgrounds from the elastic neutrino-electron scattering. It is therefore expected that the gap between the achieved sensitivity of both technologies will disappear with the next generation of experiments.

2.3 Detection Principle

So, we want to detect a single interaction happening amongst an astronomical number of particles. What does that mean with respect to detector design?

One thing which stands apart is that the background event rate should be minimum. Noble gases make an excellent candidate for detector medium since they are chemically inert. This reduces the risk of unwanted reactions within the detector. The inertness of nobles also ensure stability and longevity of the detector. Another good thing about liquid argon, and similarly for other liquid nobles, is that it scintillates in the Vacuum Ultraviolet (VUV) regime, and the interaction lengths in this regime for liquid argon are quite long. A very brief discussion on this topic can be found in chapter 4. The inertness also makes it possible to purify noble gases to quite a large extent.

The next line of thinking should be on amplification: some physical process should be exploited to amplify that single event into multiple daughter events, so that, the actual detection mechanism is not looking for just one event but several daughter events. This way, we can afford to lose a fraction of the daughter events and still make a detection. Amplification is what allows statistics to compensate for inefficiencies of

the photosensor. Without this amplification stage, there would not be any statistics to talk of. For the case of liquid argon detectors, the amplification process is provided by the liquid argon scintillation. A single scattering event by a particle would deposit some energy in the detector medium. This results into production of approximately 40,000 scintillation photons per MeV of deposited energy. If we could count the number of photons generated, we would be able to calculate how much energy was deposited in the medium.

Scintillation

A WIMP particle scattering off an argon nucleus could impart enough energy to excite the argon atom into forming an excited dimer, also known as, an excimer. The excimer decay to individual atoms in ground state by releasing a photon in wavelength range of Vacuum Ultraviolet (**VUV**). This process is known as scintillation. The argon's scintillation mechanism is depicted in figure 2.3.

Ionizing radiation interaction in liquid argon may produce scintillation light in the **VUV** regime peaking at approximately 128 nm (see figure 2.4).

Terminology Box: Radiation

Ionising Radiation: Traditionally, ionising radiation refers to both electromagnetic radiation and particles capable of ionising an atom. Throughout this thesis, the use of the term ionising radiation also includes EM radiation and particles which can cause an atom to become electronically excited. This definition of ionising radiation, while understandable to astroparticle physicists, might be quite non-conventional for nuclear and particle physicists.

Light Collection

Using the liquid argon detectors, the problem of detection of rare interactions is translated into the task of detection of photons from the scintillation of liquid argon. Now, all we need is an efficient technique for detection of scintillation photons. From what we know about argon scintillation, we can construct a scheme for collection and detection of these photons (see figure 2.5).

Conventional photosensors have low detection efficiency in VUV regime. A common approach utilised for efficient detection of VUV scintillation is by employing fluorescent materials to shift the VUV photons to visible regime, where the conventional photosensors have higher detection efficiencies. A fluorescent material when used in this application is also called a Wavelength Shifter (**WLS**). The discussion on light collection will be expanded in the chapter 4. Chapters 5 and 6 will dive deeper into wavelength shifters.

Figure 2.3: Argon scintillation mechanism. A radiation interacting with an argon atom could lead to formation of either an excited or an ionized argon atom. This ultimately leads to the formation of an excited argon molecule which would decay to individual atoms, releasing the energy in the form of a VUV photon. The stability of the excimer state determines the time profile of an event. While a singlet excimer might decay within 10 ns, a triplet excimer state takes an average of 1.5 μ s to decay. Ref [58]

Figure 2.4: Scintillation spectra of liquid (black) and gas argon (red). Ref [59]

Figure 2.5: Light collection and detection scheme in liquid argon detectors. The photosensor signals are recorded with the help of a Data Acquisition system (DAQ).

Single Photon Detection

Photosensors capable of single photon detection are required for such experiments. Recall that these experiments would need to count the number of photons generated, hence, these experiments are in the photon-counting regime. The common choices are:

1. Photomultiplier Tubes (**PMT**) are highly sensitive photodetectors that amplify an electrical signal through a cascade of secondary electron emissions across a series of dynodes, initiated by the photoelectric effect at the photocathode. Due to their high sensitivity and fast response, PMTs have been the workhorse of experimental physics since their invention in the 1930s. Numerous experiments utilise these devices, e.g., DEAP-3600 [39], Super-Kamiokande [60].
2. Single-photon Avalanche Diode (**SPAD**). SPAD are a type of photosensor operated in Geiger mode, for which biasing above the breakdown voltage can result in a self-sustaining avalanche in response to the absorption of just a single photon [61]. A SPAD is the foundational unit of a Silicon PhotoMultiplier (**SiPM**). A typical off-the-shelf SiPM would have SPAD density anywhere between 10^3 to 10^5 per mm^2 . SiPM are currently the most popular choice for constructing photon detection systems for several upcoming experiments, e.g., DarkSide-20k [62], LEGEND-1000 [63], Cherenkov Telescope Array [64].

Terminology Box: Photodetectors

I want to make a distinction between two terms which I would use frequently throughout this thesis:

Photodetection devices: Photodetection device or Photosensor or photodetector refers to the same thing: an instrument capable of sensing EM radiation. They convert EM radiation intensity to an electric quantity, e.g., charge. For example, Photomultiplier Tubes, Avalanche Photodiode, or pixelated CCD imaging sensors

Photon Detection Systems: Photon Detection System are instrument built with some elaborate scheme for EM radiation collection and detection, but the ultimate detection is done by a photosensor.

For example, X-ARAPUCA [65] devices to be used in DUNE Far Detectors.

2.4 DEAP-3600 Dark Matter Detector

DEAP-3600 [39] is a WIMP dark matter detector that utilises liquid argon to achieve exceptional sensitivity (see figure 2.6 for an overview of DEAP-3600). The design prioritises ultra-low radioactivity levels, a large liquid argon target mass, and minimal background interference, which is achieved at SNOLAB—an underground laboratory located 2 km below the surface. The rock overburden at SNOLAB provides natural shielding against cosmic-ray muons, which would otherwise hinder WIMP detection.

The detector holds 3.3 tonnes of liquid argon, providing the necessary mass to detect WIMP-nucleon scattering cross-sections as low as 10^{-46} cm² for dark matter particles with a mass of 100 GeV/c². Since the argon in DEAP-3600 is liquefied from the atmospheric air, it contains trace amounts of beta emitter ³⁹Ar with the activity of approximately 1 Bq/kg [66], which is a background mitigated with pulse shape discrimination, as discussed in detail later in chapter 3. Due to the significant event rate, DEAP-3600 is about the largest possible detector using atmospheric argon ³⁹Ar. Scaling up beyond 1-tonne scale, as in the case of the DarkSide-20k detector discussed next, requires the use of low radioactivity argon sequestered from underground gas wells.

The primary containment for the liquid argon is a 2-inch-thick acrylic vessel with an inner radius of 85 cm, designed to maintain temperatures close to -180°C. The interior of the vessel is coated with Tetraphenyl Butadiene (TPB) wavelength shifter material, which converts VUV to visible blue light, with emission peak at 420 nm. This visible light is then transmitted to 255 high quantum efficiency Hamamatsu R5912 PMTs through the acrylic. The TPB coating on 9 m² of the inner surface of the acrylic vessel has been performed in-situ using the large area vacuum evaporation process, from a single thermal evaporation source suspended in the centre, and with the entire detector converted into a large vacuum chamber [67]. In due course, practical limits of this technology have been reached, which is one of the motivations for exploring alternative polymeric wavelength shifters in this thesis.

The PMTs are separated from the acrylic vessel by acrylic light guides and polyethylene filler blocks, which serve as neutron shielding and thermal insulation. The inner detector is housed within a large stainless steel shell, submerged in an 8 m diameter ultrapure water tank. This tank is equipped with additional veto PMTs. The tank acts as a radiation shield, and Cherenkov veto to identify cosmogenic muons. The acrylic neck provides access to the interior of the vessel, while the glove box enables the insertion or extraction of process systems, resurfacing machines, TPB deployment system, and calibration sources, all within a radon-free environment.

Due to the high rate of ³⁹Ar background events, in order to minimise the amount of data the detector operates with a low level trigger, ignores those low energy and slow time constant events that definitely do not look like the expected WIMP-signal (based on a threshold on total charge collected in a short 177 ns time window). For the remaining events, for all inner detector PMTs 16 μ s long traces, which include 2.4 μ s pre-trigger window, are digitised at 250 MS/s sampling rate and saved to disk [68].

Figure 2.6: DEAP-3600 detector schematic. Ref [39].

The DEAP-3600 detector commenced physics data taking in 2015 and with a short break took data until March 2020, when, due to the imposed COVID-19 related access restrictions, it was emptied of liquid argon and secured in a safe low-maintenance state and continued to take engineering data with empty detector. In 2019 the current leading exclusion limit on WIMP-nucleus scattering in an argon target was published [68]. At that time, it also became clear that the sensitivity of the detector was limited by backgrounds from alpha radioactivity present in the neck of the detector, as well as in traces of dust suspended in liquid argon. Post-pandemic, the detector was upgraded to mitigate both issues and is now about to start the next fill with liquid argon and a physics run, aimed at achieving, and possibly exceeding, its design sensitivity.

2.5 DarkSide-20k

DarkSide-20k [62] is a next generation liquid argon detector designed for direct detection of WIMPs (see figure 2.7). This experiment utilises a dual-phase liquid argon Time Projection Chamber (TPC) to achieve unprecedented sensitivity levels.

The core of DarkSide-20k is a dual-phase TPC, which employs liquid argon as the detection medium. This design enables the experiment to effectively distinguish between nuclear and electron recoils, a crucial capability for identifying potential WIMP interactions. The detector will be filled with 50 tonnes of liquid argon sourced from underground reservoirs, significantly reducing the background radiation from ^{39}Ar , which is prevalent in atmospheric argon. This underground argon (UAr) has a ^{39}Ar content that is orders of magnitude lower than that found in atmospheric argon, thereby minimising background and enhancing the detector's sensitivity.

Figure 2.7: Schematic of the DarkSide-20k detector showing from the inside out, respectively: the TPC (gray), the neutron veto volume contained in the stainless steel tank (teal), the muon veto volume (yellow) filled with atmospheric argon and contained in a large membrane cryostat.

DarkSide-20k is, currently, under construction at the Laboratori Nazionali del

Gran Sasso (LNGS) in Italy. The laboratory's location deep within the Gran Sasso mountain provides a natural shield against cosmic radiation, ensuring a low-background environment essential for sensitive dark matter detection experiments.

The primary goal of DarkSide-20k is to detect WIMPs by observing their rare interactions with argon nuclei. The experiment aims to achieve a sensitivity to WIMP-nucleon cross-sections of approximately $1.2 \times 10^{-47} \text{ cm}^2$ for WIMPs with a mass of 1 TeV/c^2 , with the potential to extend this sensitivity over a ten-year run, see figure 2.8

Figure 2.8: Dark matter sensitivity projections for DarkSide-20k. Ref [69]

2.5.1 DarkSide-20k veto

The veto subsystem is one of the unique features of the DarkSide-20k experiment. It consists of 2 layers: the outer muon veto and the inner neutron veto that directly surrounds the TPC. Both vetos are instrumented with veto photodetector units (PDU), which are 20 cm by 20 cm arrays of SiPMs.

The muon veto, see figure 2.7, is filled with atmospheric argon contained in a ProtoDUNE-like cryostat. Because of the immense amount of scintillation generated by crossing muons, it can work with a high detection threshold, significantly above the energies expected from other natural sources of radiation, in particular above the ^{39}Ar beta spectrum endpoint.

The stainless steel tank immersed in atmospheric argon, separates the inner volume filled with underground low-radioactivity argon, with the ^{39}Ar fraction reduced by 3 orders of magnitude. The tank contains the TPC and the neutron veto, directly surrounding it. The operation principle of the neutron veto, depicted in figure 2.9, is as follows. Some of the neutrons, as they thermalise bouncing multiple

times in the detector volume, in due course may cause WIMP-like nuclear recoils in the TPC. However, thanks to the high capture cross-section on hydrogen, most of them will eventually be captured in the polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) walls of the TPC. Such captures are immediately followed by emission of a de-excitation gamma at 2.2 MeV energy, which easily leaves acrylic and causes bright, high energy events inside or outside of the TPC. While the TPC has excellent light collection and detection efficiency necessary for WIMP searches, the volume and surface area (nearly 200 m²) surrounding it are much larger and much harder to instrument with enough PDUs.

Figure 2.9: The DarkSide-20k neutron veto operation principle (see text for details). Figure courtesy: Dr Iftikhar Ahmad.

The approach taken was to only cover a small fraction of the veto surface with photosensors, but at the same time, line the walls with efficient reflectors and wavelength shifters to recover the light collection efficiency. Due to the large surface area, TPB was no longer practical, and following the proposal to the collaboration by my group and the cryogenic demonstration [70], Polyethylene Naphthalate (PEN) was chosen as the WLS. While PEN is less efficient than TPB, based on the optical Monte Carlo simulations [71] and analytic estimates based on the model from chapter 4, its performance translated into acceptable vetoing efficiency and dead-time, and also led to setting the minimum 30% requirement on the PEN wavelength-shifting efficiency with respect to TPB [72].

The current, near final, design of the arrangement of reflector and PEN foils on the surfaces of the neutron veto is shown in figure 2.10. Both types of foils have been already procured and currently, in preparation for their final preparation (cutting to size, including holes for attachment), a quality control measurements are ongoing, as described in chapter 6.

Figure 2.10: Arrangement of [WLS](#) reflector foils in the DarkSide-20k detector veto, on the outer walls of the TPC (left), and on the inner walls of the stainless steel tank (right) [73, 74]. Both surfaces are covered with partially overlapping, mainly rectangular sheets of reflector and PEN.

Chapter 3

Pulse Shape Discrimination

Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) is a technique used to identify the type of radiation based on the time profile of the pulse produced in the detector. First, I will provide a general background on PSD, followed by a discussion of its application in liquid argon experiments for dark matter searches.

The physical PSD model, the main model described in this chapter, has been under development for some time, and has received support from various researchers over the years. I will describe the idea behind this approach, and highlight my key contributions to the development of the physical PSD model and its validation with the DEAP-3600 experimental data.

This task entailed a lot of coding and debugging. In order to efficiently perform these activities, I had to develop some tools for my own use¹. I believe that a thesis should focus on the work itself rather than the tools used. Therefore, describing these tools are not described in this thesis. In this chapter, my focus will be on illustrating precisely what I contributed to, rather than how I implemented it. Of course, the code will be made available upon request.

3.1 Introduction

When designing an experiment, the choice of detection scheme will often depend on what type of radiations can be discriminated by the detector. The most common use of PSD is to discriminate between gamma and neutron radiations in organic scintillator detectors [78]. In the context of rare event searches, PSD is employed to differentiate signal from background. However, the physical processes that enable pulse shape discrimination in different detector media can be completely different.

¹For example, one problem I faced while working on this code was that some PyTorch libraries ran smoothly on the CPU but failed on the GPU or gave unexpected result due to some issues with dependencies. Since GPUs were available only on the Narval computing cluster in Canada [75], I had to submit a SLURM [76] job and wait for the resources to become available. Every time the job failed, it wasted a lot of time. To address this, I implemented a workflow that allowed me to run prototype code on the cluster in real-time. I wrote a Bash [77] script to acquire cluster resources, including GPUs, as a SLURM job and to connect my local machine to the Jupyter server running on the cluster using port forwarding. This workflow greatly accelerated the development process.

Box: Discrimination in radiation detectors

There is a very common problem in radiation detectors that they can not tell a photon apart from a particle possessing the same energy.

Such detectors might not be very useful in certain applications where the aim of the detector is to detect one kind of radiation. For example, telescopes for high energy astrophysics, such as Fermi LAT [79] are aimed at detection of gammas from astrophysical sources not charged cosmic ray particles.

A number of techniques have been developed to tackle this issue. For example, the discrimination in case of Fermi LAT is achieved with help of anti-coincidence detector [80] which is essentially an enclosure of scintillator tiles surrounding the LAT detector. Charged particles will produce scintillation in these tiles, which will be read out by wavelength shifting fibre and PMT. If a signal is detected in both the anti-coincidence detector and the LAT, it will be vetoed out. The exact mechanics of vetoing in the anti-coincidence detector are a bit complex but this explanation suffices for the purpose of this discussion.

Liquid Argon PSD

In liquid argon, the radiation causes scintillation with time profile characteristic of intermediate argon dimer states. This scintillation time becomes the basis for pulse shape discrimination in liquid argon. E.g., LAr dark matter detectors make heavy use of pulse shape discrimination for rejecting beta background generated by decay of radio active isotopes of argon.

Germanium PSD

I wanted to provide an example of an experiment where pulse shape is directly not governed by the properties of scintillation or charge collection. In experiments employing heavily shielded Germanium detectors, the pulse shape is influenced by the number of event sites. E.g., a beta particle would deposit all of its energy in one site but a high energy gamma (> 200 keV) will undergo Compton scattering causing multiple events in the Germanium crystal [81]. The figure 3.1 shows pulse shapes for a single site and a multi-site events recorded in the GERDA experiment [82].

Though, I have only given two examples of mechanisms which allow us to discriminate radiation types based on the shape of pulse generated in a detector, this by no means is an exhaustive list of such mechanisms.

Figure 3.1: Pulse Shape in Germanium detectors. Taken from Ref.[83]

3.2 PSD in liquid argon detectors for dark matter search

^{39}Ar is an unstable isotope of Argon. It is found in trace quantities in the atmospheric Argon. ^{39}Ar undergoes beta decay. The beta particles released will be registered as normal hits by the detector. For atmospheric argon, this background is large enough to drown any potential WIMP-like signal. Thus, beta particles released from ^{39}Ar form the dominant background in liquid argon WIMP detectors. PSD can be employed to discriminate beta background from genuine nuclear recoil (WIMP-like) signals.

PSD in DEAP-3600

Once, we define an appropriate metric which can use the pulse time profile to discriminate different events, we can start employing this metric to entire datasets.

There is no single universally accepted metric for this purpose. Different experiments use different metrics. One of the metrics used in DEAP-3600 is called F_{Prompt} .

If N_{Prompt} and N_{Late} are the number of prompt (arriving up to 60 ns from the event time) and late (arriving between 60 ns and 10 μs from the event time) photons, then the PSD metric F_{Prompt} can be defined in this manner:

$$F_{\text{Prompt}} = \frac{N_{\text{Prompt}}}{N_{\text{Prompt}} + N_{\text{Late}}} \quad (3.1)$$

Once F_{Prompt} is calculated for all events, the F_{Prompt} values can be plotted as function of Number of Photo-Electrons (see the figure 3.2b).

(a) PMT pulses of nuclear and electron recoil. In case of a nuclear recoil (top), most of the recorded energy comes from the beginning of the event (prompt window). In the case of electron recoil (bottom), though a large fraction of recorded energy was released in the beginning, but substantial amounts of energy are also recorded during the later parts (late window) of the event as well.

(b) nPE vs F_{prompt} plot from DEAP-3600 calibration data. Image credit: [68]

Figure 3.2: PSD in LAr

3.3 PSD Models

In this chapter, I will discuss two different approaches to Pulse Shape Discrimination.

1. An effective approach
2. A physics-based approach

3.4 Effective PSD Model

This approach employs what is known as an effective model which describes the distribution of events in the nPE vs PSD parameter space as a convolution of the Gamma and Gauss distributions:

$$\Gamma(x; \mu, b) = \frac{1}{b\mu\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{b}\right)} \left(\frac{x}{b\mu}\right)^{\frac{1}{b}-1} e^{-\frac{x}{b\mu}} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\Phi(x) = I \cdot \Gamma(x; \mu, b) * \text{Gauss}(x; \mu = 0, \sigma) \quad (3.3)$$

Where parameters b , σ , μ for a given number of scintillation photons N_{nsc} are given as follows:

$$b(N_{nsc}) = a_0 + \frac{a_1}{N_{nsc}} + \frac{a_2}{N_{nsc}^2} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\sigma(N_{nsc}) = a_3 + \frac{a_4}{N_{nsc}} + \frac{a_5}{N_{nsc}^2} \quad (3.5)$$

$$\mu(N_{nsc}) = a_6 + \frac{a_7}{N_{nsc}} + \frac{a_8}{N_{nsc}^2} + \frac{a_9}{N_{nsc}^3} \quad (3.6)$$

The equations 3.4, 3.5, and 3.6 all show empirical relationships. The parameters a_0, a_1, \dots, a_9 have no physical meaning.

The model is described in [84], from which these equations have been taken.

Appendix A demonstrates the functioning of a Python-based module I developed for DEAP-3600. This module makes use of an existing implementation of this effective model for online analysis of DEAP-3600 data during the refilling of liquid argon.

3.5 Physical PSD Model

For WIMP searches with liquid argon detectors, a robust background model is necessary, that can be reliably extrapolated orders of magnitude beyond the available data. The data driven models such as the effective model described in the previous section cannot be reliably extrapolated beyond the range of the data on which they are based. Therefore, we need a physics-based model for reliably extrapolating this background.

A physics based approach to PSD where the distribution of events in the nPE vs PSD parameter space is described by a physical model is being developed. The initial

attempt involved developing a simple analytic model [85]. However, the analytic model could not be made to fully include scintillation physics. Therefore, the focus was shifted to developing a Monte Carlo approach to the physical PSD model, such that, it could include all the processes involved in scintillation and detection of these scintillation photons.

A Monte Carlo physical-PSD model had been developed and implemented in ROOT/C++. Since, this implementation, turned out to be computationally expensive and much too slow for use as a general multi-parameter fitter for experimental data, the model was subsequently implemented in Python using the PyTorch library. PyTorch was chosen since it has the necessary mathematical function for implementing this model, and it provides an option to parallelise these computations with the mere change of an argument. The MC model was implemented in Python by Dr. Manish Gupta, Prof. Piotr Gawron, Prof. Łukasz Pawela, and others [86, 87].

While the samples are generated with PyTorch, the actual fitting is performed with TMinuit - a popular package for multiparameter fitting [88].

Steps for the calculation of PSD Parameter

1. We start with one event. Event energy is assigned an event energy, E , randomly sampled from the assumed theoretical ^{39}Ar β -decay spectrum.
2. Calculate the number of excitons from scintillation and ionization:

$$n_q = \text{int} \left(\text{Gauss} \left(E \cdot W, \sqrt{E \cdot W \cdot F_{\text{Fano}}} \right) \right) \quad (3.7)$$

where,

$$W = \frac{1}{19.5 \cdot 10^{-3}} \text{ photons/keV,}$$

Fano factor, $F_{\text{Fano}}=0.107$

3. Calculate the number of ions and excimers by binomially splitting excitons, assuming the excitation ratio $R_{\text{excit}} = 0.21$, and the recombination probability $RP = 0.7338$ [89]:

$$n_{\text{exc}} = \text{Binom} \left(n_q, \frac{R_{\text{excit}}}{1 + R_{\text{excit}}} \right) \quad (3.8)$$

$$n_{\text{ph}} = n_{\text{exc}} + \text{Binom} (n_q - n_{\text{exc}}, RP) \quad (3.9)$$

4. Binomially split photons into prompt and late populations, using the mean PSD parameter dependence on the event energy, \overline{pp} :

$$n_{ph, p} = \text{Binom} (n_{ph}, \overline{pp}(E)) \quad (3.10)$$

$$n_{ph, l} = n_{ph} - n_{ph, p} \quad (3.11)$$

5. Calculate the number of photoelectrons. The process of converting photons to photoelectrons is modelled as a Beta distribution with the mean Photon Detection Probability (PDP), \bar{p} :

$$n_{pe, p} = \text{Binom}(n_{ph, p}, \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)), \quad (3.12)$$

$$n_{pe, l} = \text{Binom}(n_{ph, l}, \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)), \quad (3.13)$$

$$\text{where,} \quad (3.14)$$

$$\alpha = n_{ph} \times b \times \bar{p} \quad (3.15)$$

$$\beta = n_{ph} \times b \times (1 - \bar{p}) \quad (3.16)$$

$$(3.17)$$

6. Add single Photo-Electron (sPE) noise (PMT charge resolution) and the electronic noise:

$$\sigma_{spe, p}^2 = \epsilon_{spe}^2 \times n_{pe, p} \quad (3.18)$$

$$\sigma_{spe, l}^2 = \epsilon_{spe}^2 \times n_{pe, l} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\sigma_p^2 = \sigma_{spe, p}^2 + \sigma_{elec, p}^2 \quad (3.20)$$

$$\sigma_l^2 = \sigma_{spe, l}^2 + \sigma_{elec, l}^2 \quad (3.21)$$

$$n'_{pe, p} = \max(0, \text{Gauss}(n_{pe, p}, \sigma_p)) \quad (3.22)$$

$$n'_{pe, l} = \max(0, \text{Gauss}(n_{pe, l}, \sigma_l)). \quad (3.23)$$

Where, the ϵ_{spe} parameter's value typically lies in the range 0.25 ± 0.14 , and $\sigma_{elec, p}$ and $\sigma_{elec, l}$ can be in the 0.01-10 range.

7. Then add the window noise.

$$\sigma_{w, pl} = \text{Gauss}(0, \epsilon_w \times n'_{pe, l}) \quad (3.24)$$

$$n''_{pe, l} = n'_{pe, l} + \sigma_{w, pl} + \delta_l \quad (3.25)$$

$$n''_{pe, p} = n'_{pe, p} - \sigma_{w, pl} + \delta_p \quad (3.26)$$

$$(3.27)$$

where, instrumental offsets is modelled with $\delta_{l, p}$.

8. And finally, calculate the event PSD parameter

$$pp = \frac{n''_{pe, p}}{n''_{pe, p} + n''_{pe, l}} \quad (3.28)$$

The parameters can be kept fixed, or free for the fit. The model is summarised in the block diagram shown in the figure 3.3.

Ref: *Astroparticle Physics* **85** (2016) 1-23

Ref: M Szydagis et al 2011 *JINST* **6** P10002

Figure 3.3: Monte Carlo Physical PSD model. Ref [90]

3.5.1 Fitter verification

I have been having trouble fitting DEAP-3600 experimental data with this code. To investigate the source of the problem, I initially started to investigate the fitter itself. First, I generate approximately 3×10^6 events for a set of fixed parameters using this model. This event volume is equivalent to approximately one day of DEAP-3600 data. I call this ‘fake data’. Then, this fake data is fed to the fitter as input. The fitter has been shown to be capable of fitting this fake data, as shown in the figure 3.4.

3.5.2 Fits to DEAP-3600 Experimental data

It turns out that using a smaller set of experimental data—about one day of detector data from DEAP-3600—the code could achieve a satisfactory level of agreement with the data. The figure 3.5b shows the results of multiparameter fit to DEAP-3600 detector data.

3.5.3 Photon Detection Probability

Since, it was noted that the fitter fails to fit higher statistics experimental data, it was natural to suspect that the issue could be with the evolution of PDP. As explained earlier, we model the PDP as a beta distribution. The beta distribution is supposed to capture the evolution of PDP, but it was possible that it was failing to do so. Therefore, we wanted to test whether replacing the beta distribution with some other distribution would result into a better fit. We can use distribution of empirically calculated PDP. We implemented the feature to switch to different PDP distributions. These are the available choices of alternative distributions:

1. An empirically determined time distribution of PDP values (figure 3.6a). The average PDP of DEAP-3600 changes over time. This distribution was made from PDP time evolution curve generously provided by the Dr Joe McLaughlin.
2. A distribution of PDP values in different position inside the detector determined with a Monte Carlo simulation (figure 3.6b). The PDP is not uniform across the detector volume. Rather, it varies by position inside the detector. It is difficult to empirically determine the PDP variation inside the detector. As a starting point, we used a position dependent PDP distribution obtained from a toy Monte Carlo simulation of the DEAP-3600 detector. The simulation was done by Prof Marcin Kuźniak.
3. A convolution of these two distributions (figure 3.6c). A convolution would capture both the time evolution and the position dependence of PDP.

With help of Prof Gawron, I implemented an efficient sampling algorithm to produce a one dimensional vector from the chosen distribution on each iteration of the sampler. The choice of distribution can be specified from a config file.

However, this neither improved nor worsen the fit. At this point, it is fair to believe that the issue might reside elsewhere.

A list of possible model fixes is given below:

(a) nPE vs F_{Prompt} plot for self-consistency check. The data was generated by the code for a set of fixed parameters.

(b) Fitter verification plot.

Figure 3.4: Plots for self-consistency check. The low value of χ^2/ν indicates the code is able to fit the ‘ideal’ data.

(a) nPE vs F_{prompt} plot. Bottom left part of spectrum trimmed due to DAQ trigger

(b) F_{prompt} vs probability plot

Figure 3.5: Plots for DEAP-3600 experimental data.

(a) LY distribution made from empirically determined time evolution of LY. This can be translated into the PDP distribution as $PDP = LY/SY$

(b) PDP MC position distribution

(c) PDP distribution convolution. Distribution smoothed with a Gaussian filter.

Figure 3.6: Photon Detection Probability distributions available in Physical PSD code.

1. Using different parameter pairs, i.) Fprompt60 and qPE, and ii.) Rprompt60 and nSCBayes.
2. Including TPB multiphoton emission.
3. Including anti-correlation for late and prompt scintillation photons.
4. Using same detection probability for prompt and late photons in the same event.
5. Using an alternate theoretical ^{39}Ar beta decay spectrum.
6. Including Cherenkov background component.

The fixes, listed above, have not yet been investigated and are left for future development.

3.5.4 A comment on the code diagnostics

I found that when using PyTorch on a GPU, fixing the seed in PyTorch and NumPy doesn't ensure consistent random number generator state.

Each time the code is run, it follows a different path, making it hard to tell if changes in fitted parameters are due to code modifications or randomness. This complicates debugging. It appears that this issue is specific to our code and not a general PyTorch bug, and it only occurs on the GPU.

The plots in figure 3.7 show the problem by repeat execution of the code with and without fixing the seed.

3.6 Summary

In liquid argon dark matter experiments, Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) is crucial for suppressing the dominant background from the beta decay of ^{39}Ar . This chapter presents an overview of efforts to develop and validate a physics-based Monte Carlo approach to pulse shape discrimination for such experiments. In addition to generating Monte Carlo samples, the code can also fit the model to experimental data. It is implemented in Python and utilises PyTorch for parallel computing on a GPU. Future updates are planned to enable the use of distributed computing for multi-GPU processing.

I validated the fitter to ensure its reliability. Additionally, a trigger cut was successfully implemented for application to the simulated data, mirroring the DAQ trigger in DEAP-3600. A new feature was introduced to allow switching between different empirical PDP distributions and a beta distribution, providing greater flexibility in modelling. During this process, an issue related to the reproducibility of the fit was identified, warranting further investigation of the code. While significant progress has been made, complete agreement with DEAP-3600 experimental data has not yet been achieved. Further refinement of the model is necessary and will be addressed in future work.

Figure 3.7: The physical PSD code is executed 100 times and the reduced chi-square (χ^2/ν) is recorded. The left column shows the χ^2/ν values as a function of the execution index. The right column shows the distribution of these χ^2/ν values along with the mean, standard deviation, and the ratio of maximum to minimum of these values. The first row is for the case when the seed is not fixed, and the second row for the case when the seed is fixed. There is no significant between difference between each of the cases, indicating that fixing the seed has doesn't actually work. This has severe repercussion for the code diagnostics.

Chapter 4

An Analytic Model for Estimation of Light Yield

The chapters 5 and 6 will discuss the quantification of wavelength shifting capabilities of PEN sheets for use in liquid argon detectors. Before we can discuss that, we need to form an understanding about how the light is generated inside the detector, and how it is detected. I will discuss an analytic model developed for estimation of light detected in liquid argon detectors. The discussion in this chapter is relevant not only to liquid argon detectors, but also to any detector using liquefied noble gas as the target material.

In the subsection 4.8.1, I will demonstrate the application of the model presented in this chapter for the cross-validation of a Monte Carlo simulation which was used for extracting the value of Wavelength Shifting Efficiency (WLSE) from measured light yield of a liquid argon experiment called 2PAC. This experiment was designed, built, and operated by members of our group and collaborators before I joined the effort. Here my contribution is limited to measurement of reflectance of SiPM, and cross-validation of MC simulation with the analytic model. Nevertheless, both were essential to extract the intrinsic WLSE of PEN foil in conditions representative of a real dark matter detector.

In the subsection 4.9.1, I will demonstrate how we were able to use the analytic model for cross-validating MC simulations developed for the DarkSide-20k Neutron veto detector. Throughout this chapter, I will show comparison with MC simulations, which are developed either by other members of our group or other collaborators. The analytic model is largely based on the formalism published by Segreto [91] where, in particular, I have adapted techniques from this paper for including the effect of absorption and Rayleigh scattering. Nevertheless, I have implemented it in a fully general manner with the capability of using it with experimentally measured or literature based spectra for scintillation, re-emission, reflectance and photon detection efficiency, turning it into a powerful tool, which has not been widely available until now. Furthermore, in the subsection 4.3.3, I introduce a modification to include the effect of finite probability of VUV photons reflecting from the surfaces, which is not included in the original publication. I developed a code for predicting LY for liquid argon detectors based on this model.

To recap, this chapter will demonstrate the usefulness of the analytic code in the development of sophisticated MC simulations, specially, those used for extracting the value of wavelength shifting efficiencies from experimental studies. I believe this code would prove to be an essential tool in the experimentalist's utility belt.

4.1 Introduction

Light Yield (**LY**) is the most common metric used for quantification of scintillation light produced in the detector. We define **LY** as the number of photoelectrons generated per unit of deposited energy in the detector. We can rewrite **LY** as a product of Scintillation Yield, Light Collection Efficiency, and Photon Detection Efficiency. Scintillation Yield (**SY**) is the number of scintillation photons generated per unit of deposited energy. Light Collection Efficiency (**LCE**) is the fraction of photons which will survive wavelength shifting, reflection, scattering, and absorption to be registered by the photosensor. Photon Detection Efficiency (**PDE**) is the probability that a photosensor produces an output signal in response to an incident photon.

For the scintillation photon of wavelength λ_{scint} , and shifted photon having wavelength λ_{shift} , the **LY** can be calculated using the following relation:

$$LY(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}) = SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times LCE(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}, E_{wls}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \quad (4.1)$$

where,

SS = Argon scintillation spectrum

λ_{scint} = Wavelength of a photon from the argon scintillation spectrum

λ_{shift} = Wavelength of a photon emitted from **WLS**

E_{wls} = Emission spectrum of the wavelength shifter

Note that, in principle, emission spectrum depends on the excitation wavelength. Integration of $SS(\lambda_{scint})$ over the entire liquid argon scintillation spectra gives the scintillation yield:

$$SY = \int SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times d\lambda_{scint} \quad (4.2)$$

The total **LY** can be calculated in two steps:

1. Integrate **LY** expression over entire emission spectrum of **WLS**:

$$LY(\lambda_{scint}) = \int_{E_{wls}} LY(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift}$$

$$LY(\lambda_{scint}) = \int_{E_{wls}} SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times LCE(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}, E_{wls}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift} \quad (4.3)$$

2. Integrating over entire argon scintillation spectrum

$$LY = \int_{SS} \int_{E_{wls}} (SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times LCE(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}, E_{wls}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift})) \times d\lambda_{shift} \times d\lambda_{scint} \quad (4.4)$$

Since, I define LCE in such a manner that it accounts for the probability of survival of scintillation photons, shifting efficiency to higher wavelengths, and the probability of survival of shifted photons, LCE depends on both the wavelength of scintillation photon and that of shifted photon. It also depends on the emission spectrum and WLSE of the WLS.

SY for liquid argon is fixed and is known to be approximately 40,000 photons per MeV of deposited energy [92]. PDE is a wavelength dependent quantity and specific to each photosensor, generally provided by the manufacturer. LCE, on the other hand, is specific to each detector, and is dictated by the detector geometry along with the wavelength shifting efficiency of the WLS.

One way to calculate LCE is by building a physics model of the detector and performing a ray-tracing Monte Carlo (MC) simulation using software such as GEANT4 [93]. This gives very accurate results but requires considerable effort. In the section 4.2, I will present an approach based on an analytic model for estimating light yield of liquid argon detectors. I derive an analytic expression that serves as a quick tool for estimating light yield at the expense of some accuracy, re-implementing an existing technique with a more convenient formalism suited to my purpose and further extending its formalism [91]. I developed computing tools for light yield estimation based on the analytic model and cross-verified these estimates against both Monte Carlo simulations and experimental measurement. I have designated the model and associated tools as Analytic Model for Estimation of Light Yield (AMELY).

Later sections of this chapter will demonstrate the utility of these tools in my research. The analytic model is not supposed to replace the detailed MC simulations. It is more useful while the detector is still in the design process and design is changing rather quickly. Later sections will show that the analytic model and MC simulations play a complementary role while designing liquid argon detectors.

4.2 Light Collection Efficiency

With the motivation for developing this analytic model at hand, let us try to understand the model. In this model, I create the simplistic picture of the detector. Only the interior of the detector is considered. I will consider a spherical volume containing the scintillator material. The scintillator in our case would be liquefied argon gas. There are two types of interior surfaces:

- a) the detector surface instrumented with photosensors such as Silicon Photomultipliers

- b) the detector surface covered with the wavelength shifter, hereafter referred to as the wall. The wall not only needs to wavelength shift the scintillation light but also to reflect the light back into the detector volume, there-by, enhancing the light collection. Therefore, the wavelength shifters are often backed by a highly reflective surface. We call this combination as a Wavelength Shifting Reflector ([WLSR](#)).

In such detectors, all surfaces are covered either with the photosensor or the WLSR to maximise the light collection. There will be inefficiencies in covering the surface with WLSR. I will account for these inefficiencies in the average reflectance and effective wavelength shifting efficiency of the wall.

Light goes through the following stages:

1. Genesis: radiation passing through the target material may cause creation of scintillation light in the detector. For liquid argon, these are VUV photons peaking at around 128 nm
2. VUV propagation: VUV photon propagate through the medium. The VUV photons can undergo scattering or absorption or go unaffected through the medium.
3. VUV interactions with optical boundaries: There are two optical boundaries: the photosensors, and the wall. Either of these might reflect or absorb the VUV photons.
4. Wavelength Shifting: VUV photons incident on the wavelength shifter have a finite probability that they will be absorbed, and new visible photons will be re-emitted. For a bulk material of randomly oriented molecules, we can treat remission to be isotropic.
5. Visible propagation: visible photons propagate through the medium with finite interaction lengths.
6. Visible interactions with optical interfaces: The visible photons might meet their demise at the optical boundaries, as they might get absorbed there. The visible photons might be reflected as well.
7. Light detection: visible photons can be detected by the photosensors.

The figure [4.1](#) illustrates different schemes in which photons can make their way to a photosensor.

For building a foundational model, I will assume that the absorption is negligible, and thus can be ignored from the LCE calculation. I will divide this task into two parts. I will separately consider the cases of the visible photons, and VUV photons. In the end, I will combine these two to get the final LCE value.

Figure 4.1: Different ways in which light can be collected. The liquid argon volume is represented by the blue circle. The photosensors are represented by the orange rectangles. The wall is represented by the grey annular ring. Stars show the event origin location. Dashed lines represent VUV photons, while solid lines represent visible photons. Blue event is applicable only when the photosensor is sensitive to scintillation light.

4.2.1 Visible Photons

Essentially, we want to know what fraction of visible photons produced in the detector will survive to cause a photoelectric effect in the photosensor. I will use the parameter Photon Survival Probability (**PSP**) for quantification of the probability of photons surviving the optical interaction in the detector: reflection, scatter, and absorption. Note that PSP is wavelength dependent. I will ignore absorption at the surface of photosensor. Also, not all the photons that make it past the photosensor surface are registered. The PDE parameter accounts for that.

A photon can undergo one of the following interactions with the interior surfaces of the detector:

1. A visible photon might enter the photo-sensitive region of the photosensor without getting reflected. I refer to this as ‘light collection’. I denote the

probability of this happening as X

2. It might be reflected by the wall. I denote the probability of this happening as w
3. It might be reflected by the photosensor. I denote the probability of this happening as s

PSP_{Vis} is the probability that a visible photon survives all the reflections etc to be collected by the photosensor. After each time a photon is reflected back into the detector medium, I calculate the probability of it entering the photosensor. The probability is equal to reflectance of that optical boundary. This is done iteratively infinitely. Since the probability is a number less than unity, the fraction of the photons entering the photosensor gets smaller and smaller after each reflection. Thus, this summation will form a convergent series.

I will do this iteratively, in the first iteration X fraction of total photon will be collected.

$$PSP_{iteration=1} = X \quad (4.5)$$

At this stage, there are w photons reflected by wall and s photons reflected by the photosensor. Thus, total $w + s$ photons are available for second iteration. Only the number of available photons in the detector has changed, this does not change the probability of photons making it to the photosensor. Therefore, I can write the fraction of the photons which will be collected in this iteration as follow:

$$PSP_{iteration=2} = X \times (s + w) \quad (4.6)$$

For the next iteration, there are $w(s + w)$ photons reflected by wall and $s(s + w)$ photons reflected by the photosensor. Thus, total $w(s + w) + s(s + w)$ photons are available for second iteration. I can write the fraction of the photons which will be collected in this iteration as follow:

$$PSP_{iteration=2} = X \times [w(s + w) + s(s + w)] \quad (4.7)$$

The pattern will continue and I can write rest of the terms arising from this pattern. Thus, I can write the PSP_{Vis} as follow:

$$PSP_{Vis} = X + X \times [s + w] + X \times [s(s + w) + w[s + w]] + X \times [s(s + w)^2 + w[s + w]^2] + X \times [s(s + w)^3 + w[s + w]^3] + \dots \quad (4.8)$$

I can simplify the expression in the right hand side of the above equation:

$$PSP_{Vis} = X + X \times (s + w) + X \times (s + w)^2 + X \times (s + w)^3 + X \times (s + w)^4 + \dots \quad (4.9)$$

I will write the above equation in a condensed form below:

$$PSP_{Vis} = X \times \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (s + w)^r \quad (4.10)$$

The expression in the right hand side is the sum of the terms of a Geometric Progression. The sum of such series is well known:

$$PSP_{Vis} = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} X \times \frac{1 - (s + w)^r}{1 - (s + w)} \quad (4.11)$$

Under the condition that $s + w < 1$ and $r \rightarrow \infty$, the right hand side can be approximated to:

$$PSP_{Vis} = \frac{X}{1 - (s + w)} \quad (4.12)$$

I can calculate the values of s , w , and X using the following quantities:

f_{sen} = fraction of surface covered with photosensors in percentage

PDE = Photon Detection Efficiency of the photosensor

R = reflectance of photosensor in percentage

R_{wall} = reflectance of the wall in percentage

FF_{sys} = Fraction of active area on a single photosensor

s = fraction of photons reflected by photosensors

w = fraction of photons reflected by the wall

X = fraction of photons that will enter the active region of photosensor

From the above definitions, I can derive the following expressions:

$$s = f_{sen}R \quad (4.13)$$

$$w = (1 - f_{sen})R_{wall} \quad (4.14)$$

$$X = f_{sen}FF_{sys}(1 - R) \quad (4.15)$$

I can rewrite the equation 4.12 in terms of physical quantities by substituting the values of s , w and X from equations 4.13, 4.14, and 4.15 respectively:

$$PSP_{Vis} = \frac{f_{sen} F F_{sys} (1 - R)}{1 - (f_{sen} R + (1 - f_{sen}) R_{wall})} \quad (4.16)$$

This is a nice expression for calculating how many visible photons will survive after suffering reflections in the detector. However, this is not the same as LCE, since we start with VUV photons, and this expression does not yet account for the vanishing of VUV photons due to absorption. In the following section, I will use the same technique to calculate how many VUV will survive and be shifted. Since neither the scintillation nor the fluorescence produce monochromatic light, I will later drive a wavelength dependent expression.

I generated several plots from this analytic model to demonstrate the dependence of PSP_{Vis} on detector parameters, e.g, reflectance of WLSR etc. Such plots helped me develop an intuitive understanding of the detector performance.

Figure 4.2a shows the relation between PSP and the fraction of surface area covered with photosensors. Figure 4.2b shows the relation between PSP and the reflectance of the detector inner surfaces, also referred to as the wall. As one can see, reflectance of the wall has a dramatic effect on the photon survival probability. This stresses the need for high reflectance of wavelength shifting reflectors for liquid argon detectors. The overall effect of reflectance of the photosensor on survival probability of visible photons is shown in the figure 4.2c. The survival rate of these photons decreases with increase of photosensor reflectance. Therefore, photosensors for such detectors, e.g., SiPM often employ an anti-reflection coating [94].

4.2.2 VUV Photons

I can estimate the probability of VUV photons surviving the reflections and making it to wavelength shifters. Following the discussion in subsection 4.2.1, I can derive the expression for the probability of survival of VUV photons which will reach the wall and not get reflected in the following manner:

$$PSP_{VUV} = \frac{(1 - f_{sen})(1 - R_{wall, VUV})}{1 - (s_{VUV} + w_{VUV})} \quad (4.17)$$

$$PSP_{VUV} = \frac{Y_{VUV}}{1 - (s_{VUV} + w_{VUV})} \quad (4.18)$$

Where, $Y_{VUV} = (1 - f_{sen})(1 - R_{wall, VUV})$

Note: In case of visible photons the symbol PSP_{Vis} was used to refer to the probability of a photon reaching the photosensor while in case of VUV photons the symbol PSP_{VUV} refers to the probability of a photon reaching the wall.

Just as I did in the previous subsection, I generated plots using equation 4.18 to demonstrate the dependence of PSP_{VUV} on detector parameters (see figure 4.3). One thing that becomes apparent from figures 4.3c and 4.3b is that the dependence on

(c) PSP_{Vis} as function of reflectance of photosensors (R)Figure 4.2: Dependence of Photon Survival Probability of visible photons (PSP_{Vis}) on detector parameters

the reflectances is not so strong as it was in the case of PSP_{Vis} . Comparing the PSP values in figures 4.2 and 4.3, it also becomes evident that for the case considered, the probability of a VUV photon generated in the scintillator volume to reach the wall is higher than the probability of a visible photon getting collected. Later in the section 4.3, I will discuss a method for introducing the effect of absorption and Rayleigh scattering in liquid argon.

4.2.3 VUV to Visible Conversion

The survival probability of a VUV photon tells us how many VUV photons will survive to interact with a WLSR and cause a fluorescence. I need another parameter to tell us how many visible photons will be generated by these incident VUV photons. I define **WLSE** as the average number of visible photon generated by the WLSR for each incident VUV photon. I use ϵ_{wls} to represent the effective average wavelength shifting efficiency of the material.

I can compute the average number of visible photons generated for a VUV photon:

$$n_{VUV2Vis} = \epsilon_{wls} \times PSP_{VUV} \quad (4.19)$$

Since LCE is nothing but the fraction of these visible photons surviving the reflections to arrive at the photosensors, I can derive the expression for LCE:

$$LCE = PSP_{VUV} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times PSP_{Vis} \quad (4.20)$$

Substituting the values of PSP from equations 4.12 and 4.18 in equation 4.20:

$$LCE = \frac{Y_{VUV}}{1 - (s_{VUV} + w_{VUV})} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times \frac{X_{Vis}}{1 - (s_{Vis} + w_{Vis})} \quad (4.21)$$

Using the equation 4.17, it can be shown that for a liquid argon detector with photosensor coverage of the about 1%, the $PSP_{VUV} \approx 1$ (figure 4.3a).

Thus, we can write the LCE as follows:

$$LCE \approx \epsilon_{wls} \times \frac{X_{Vis}}{1 - (s_{Vis} + w_{Vis})} \quad (4.22)$$

The equation 4.21 is a very important result, as we can use it in the following applications:

- Detector design: we can quickly estimate LY for different detector configurations by using this LCE value as described in section 4.1
- Estimating WLSE: we can infer the ϵ_{wls} of a wavelength shifting material from the measured LY of the detector.

(c) PSP_{VUV} as function of R_{VUV} Figure 4.3: Dependence of PSP_{VUV} on detector parameters

4.3 Interactions in Liquid Argon

For design of large scale detectors, absorption of light and Rayleigh scattering in liquid argon would start to become an important consideration. I will improve the model presented here by including these effects. This is achieved by modifying the expressions for PSP_{Vis} and PSP_{VUV} as shown in [91].

4.3.1 PSP inclusive of Rayleigh scattering and Absorption

If U_{RA} is the probability of interaction, either absorption or Rayleigh scattering, before a photon completes one step, we define new X , s , and w parameters to account for absorption and Rayleigh scattering:

$$X_{RA} = U_{RA} \times X \quad (4.23)$$

$$(s_{RA} + w_{RA}) = U_{RA} \times (s + w) + (1 - U_{RA}) \times \frac{\lambda_{eff}}{\lambda_R} \quad (4.24)$$

Where,

$$U_{RA} = \int_0^\infty P(x) e^{-\frac{x}{\lambda_{eff}}} dx \quad (4.25)$$

λ_{abs} = interaction length of absorption

λ_R = interaction length of Rayleigh scattering

λ_{eff} = effective interaction length

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{eff}} = \frac{1}{\lambda_{abs}} + \frac{1}{\lambda_R} \quad (4.26)$$

$P(x)$ is the probability density function of the distances that a photon can travel in absence of interactions between two reflections or a reflection and an absorption/detection.

If we define L_{char} to be some characteristic length of the detector, L_{char} can be formulated in this manner:

$$L_{char} = 6 \times \frac{\text{volume}}{\text{surface_area}} \quad (4.27)$$

And, assuming $P(x)$ to be uniform between the 0 and L_{char} :

$$P(x) = \frac{1}{L_{char}} \quad (4.28)$$

Using newly defined X_{RA} , s_{RA} , and w_{RA} , we can rewrite the expression for PSP while accounting for finite probability of an interaction in liquid argon:

$$PSP = \frac{X_{RA}}{1 - (s_{RA} + w_{RA})} \quad (4.29)$$

On substituting values of X_{RA} , s_{RA} , and w_{RA} from equations 4.23 and 4.24 and rearranging terms:

$$PSP = \frac{X}{Q - (s + w)} \quad (4.30)$$

Where,

$$Q = \frac{1 - (1 - U_{RA}) \times \frac{\lambda_{eff}}{\lambda_R}}{U_{RA}} \quad (4.31)$$

$$PSP(Q, f_{sen}, FF_{sys}, R, R_{wall}) = \frac{f_{sen} FF_{sys} (1 - R)}{Q - (f_{sen} R + (1 - f_{sen}) R_{wall})} \quad (4.32)$$

I can use the equation 4.30 to modify the equation 4.12 and 4.18 to include the effects of interaction in liquid argon:

$$PSP_{Vis} = \frac{X_{Vis}}{Q_{Vis} - (s_{Vis} + w_{Vis})} \quad (4.33)$$

$$PSP_{VUV} = \frac{Y_{VUV}}{Q_{VUV} - (s_{VUV} + w_{VUV})} \quad (4.34)$$

I will use the equations 4.33 and 4.34 to expand the equation 4.20:

$$LCE = \frac{Y_{VUV}}{Q_{VUV} - (s_{VUV} + w_{VUV})} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times \frac{X_{Vis}}{Q_{Vis} - (s_{Vis} + w_{Vis})} \quad (4.35)$$

In the equation 4.35, the absorption and Rayleigh scattering effects are contained in the Q parameter. In the next subsection, I will show how these interactions lengths and the detector dimensions impact the Q parameter. In the subsection 4.9.4, I will show how L_{char} impacts the Light Yield.

4.3.2 Q parameter

So far, the light collection efficiency of a liquid argon detector was independent of the physical dimensions of the detector. Since the extent to which interactions in liquid argon impact the LCE also depend on the detector dimensions, and the Q parameter is the only term that contains the L_{char} term, the entire effect of the size of the detector is determined by this Q parameter. The figure 4.4 shows values of Q parameter as a function of characteristic length. I calculated and marked the characteristic lengths for various liquid argon detectors in this figure. Since these interaction lengths are wavelength dependent quantities [95], Q parameter for visible photons is different from Q parameters for VUV photons.

If one wants to compare detectors using different scintillator materials, then they will have to consider the interaction lengths as well. The figure 4.5 shows how the Q parameter depends on absorption and Rayleigh scattering lengths. This figure is inspired from [91]. Remember, the larger the Q, the lower the survival probability.

Figure 4.4: (top panel) Q_{VUV} as a function of L_{char} . (bottom panel) Q_{Vis} as a function of L_{char} . For liquid argon, the impact introduced by Q_{Vis} for most detectors is very small; only the DUNE Far Detector (Horizontal Drift) [96] has a relatively large value of Q_{Vis} . Q_{VUV} exceeds 1.2 for DarkSide-20k muon veto. From figure 4.6 it becomes evident that at $Q_{VUV} = 1.2$, survival probability goes down by about 20%.

(a) Q as function of λ_R for different values of λ_{abs} . Both quantities are in units of L_{char} .

(b) Q as function of λ_{abs} for different values of λ_R . Both quantities are in units of L_{char} .

Figure 4.5: The Q parameter has strong dependence on λ_{abs} while the dependence on λ_R is not so strong.

4.3.3 Approximation in PSP for VUV photons

The equation for calculating LCE shown in equation 4.35 differs from the expression derived in reference [91]. This happens because I am accounting for the finite reflectance of the photosensor and the wall for VUV photons. If I were to assume that, $R_{VUV} \approx 0$ and $R_{wall, VUV} \approx 0$ are appropriate approximations for the purpose of this calculation, I can reduce the equation 4.34:

$$PSP_{VUV} \approx \frac{1 - f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \quad (4.36)$$

I can make use of the equation 4.36 to reduce the equation 4.35:

$$LCE \approx \frac{1 - f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times \frac{X_{Vis}}{Q_{Vis} - (s_{Vis} + w_{Vis})} \quad (4.37)$$

The equation 4.37 is equivalent to the expression derived in reference [91].

However, this approximation causes a slight overestimation of the LCE. Since AMELY accounts for the fact that a small number of VUV photons incident on the wall will be reflected, the PSP from AMELY is slightly reduced in comparison to reference [91]. The figure 4.6 shows a comparison between PSP values calculated from the equation derived in this thesis and the one derived in reference [91]. The question, now, is which approach to use? As can be seen from the figure 4.6, the error exceeds 2% at $Q_{VUV} \approx 1.3$ which means the error becomes significant only when the characteristic length of the detector exceeds 6 m. To translate Q figure into characteristic length see figure 4.4. Therefore, I would argue that the correction introduced by AMELY is not significant for tabletop setups like 2PAC but it becomes significant for large detectors, e.g., the muon veto of DarkSide-20k. It is difficult to get precise measurements of reflectances at 128 nm, therefore, I used approximate values of $R_{VUV} = 15\%$ for SiPM photosensors and $R_{wall, VUV} = 10\%$ for PEN. The value $R_{VUV} = 10\%$ for SiPM is based on the reflectance measurements reported in [94]. There is no measurement of VUV reflectance at PEN. However, polymeric films usually have VUV reflectance from a few percent to 20% [97]. I am showing the effect that AMELY introduces for a moderate $R_{wall, VUV} = 10\%$. According to this model, survival probability is not very sensitive to $R_{wall, VUV}$. In a simplistic scenario where $Q_{VUV} = 1$, figure 4.3b shows us that an increase in $R_{wall, VUV}$ from 5% to 50%, only results in a drop in the survival probability of about 1%. I would emphasise that we should also keep in mind that this approach is only going to provide an approximate estimate for LCE.

Figure 4.6: PSP_{VUV} as a function of Q_{VUV} : comparison between [91] and AMELY. The error %age between two approaches is shown in red.

4.4 Photosensor covered with Wavelength Shifter

Sometimes, it is desirable to employ photosensors covered with a wavelength shifter. The detector is the same as before, except all the photosensors are covered with a wavelength shifter. I can calculate the LCE in such scenarios using AMELY.

1. VUV photon wavelength shifted at the photosensor window and collected by the photosensor:

Similar to equation 4.36, the probability of a VUV photon reaching a photosensor is close to f_{sen}/Q_{VUV} . The number of visible photons generated at photosensor would be $\epsilon_{wls} \times f_{sen}/Q_{VUV}$. Since the fluorescence is almost isotropic, half of the generated visible photons will go towards the photosensor window while the other half will be released into the scintillator volume. Thus, the number of visible photons which get collected at the photosensor for each VUV photon generated in the detector can be calculated in this manner:

$$n_{vis, sensor-collected} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \epsilon_{wls} \times (1 - R) \quad (4.38)$$

Note: In case of a polymeric wavelength shifter such as PEN, some photon will suffer multiple reflections between the photosensor window and the wavelength shifter. Some of these photons will be eventually collected by the photosensor, some will be released to the scintillator volume, and others will be absorbed at one of the optical boundaries. I am neglecting all such photons, as it will be a small number.

2. VUV photon wavelength shifted at the photosensor window but released into the scintillator volume:

The visible photons which are generated in the previous step but got released into the scintillator volume will propagate through the scintillator volume and can be treated in exactly the same manner as the visible photons generated at the wall. We already know the number of visible photons released from the previous step:

$$n_{vis, \text{ sensor-released}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \epsilon_{wls} \quad (4.39)$$

3. VUV photons wavelength shifted at the wall:

The visible photon generated at the wall will propagate through the scintillator volume. We can use the equation 4.36 to calculate the approximate number of visible photons generated at the wall:

$$n_{vis, \text{ wall}} = \frac{1 - f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \epsilon_{wls} \quad (4.40)$$

4. Propagation and collection of visible photons:

The visible photon generated in the previous two steps will propagate through the scintillator volume and eventually get collected or absorbed according to PSP_{Vis} as described in the subsection 4.2.1.

5. Net LCE:

We can calculate the net LCE by summing up the number of all the photons generated from all these steps:

$$LCE = n_{vis, \text{ sensor-collected}} + (n_{vis, \text{ sensor-released}} + n_{vis, \text{ wall}}) \times PSP_{Vis} \quad (4.41)$$

Using equations 4.38, and 4.39, and 4.40:

$$LCE = \frac{1}{2} \frac{f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \epsilon_{wls} \times (1 - R) + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \epsilon_{wls} + \frac{1 - f_{sen}}{Q_{VUV}} \epsilon_{wls} \right) \times \frac{X_{Vis}}{Q_{Vis} - (s_{Vis} + w_{Vis})} \quad (4.42)$$

Thus, the LCE of a liquid argon detector where the photosensors are covered with a WLS can be calculated using the equation 4.42.

4.5 Light Yield

The wavelength shifters are not monochromatic. Each wavelength shifter has a different emission spectrum. These visible photons having different wavelengths will have different reflectances at different surfaces and those reflected photons will then

have different probabilities of being detected as PDE is wavelength dependent as well. Recall equation 4.4:

$$LY = \int_{SS} \int_{E_{wls}} SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times LCE(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}, E_{wls}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift} \times d\lambda_{scint}$$

I can expand the expression for LCE using the equation 4.20 for the case where the photosensor are not covered with a wavelength shifter:

$$LY = \int_{SS} \int_{E_{wls}} SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times PSP_{VUV}(\lambda_{scint}) \times \epsilon_{wls} \times E_{wls}(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}) \times PSP_{Vis}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift} \times d\lambda_{scint} \quad (4.43)$$

Where, $E_{wls}(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift})$ is the normalized emission spectrum of the wavelength shifter excited with wavelength λ_{scint} .

As already discussed in subsection 4.3.3 the reflectances in VUV regime are difficult to measure, therefore, I will approximate these reflectances with a mean reflectance value for each surface considered. Also, recall that the PSP_{VUV} does not have strong dependence on reflectance (see fig 4.3c). Thus, I will use a mean PSP_{VUV} for the entire emission spectrum. The WLSE ϵ_{wls} is a scalar by definition. Therefore, these quantities can be taken out of the integral.

$$LY = \overline{PSP}_{VUV} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times \int_{SS} \int_{E_{wls}} SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times E_{wls}(\lambda_{scint}, \lambda_{shift}) \times PSP_{Vis}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift} \times d\lambda_{scint} \quad (4.44)$$

It should be noted that the emission spectra of both wavelength shifters, i.e., Polyethylene Naphthalate (PEN) and TPB do not have strong dependence on the excitation wavelength [98]. Therefore, I can make an approximation that E_{wls} is a function only of λ_{shift} :

$$LY = \overline{PSP}_{VUV} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times \int_{SS} \int_{E_{wls}} SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times E_{wls}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PSP_{Vis}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift} \times d\lambda_{scint} \quad (4.45)$$

Rearranging terms and spitting integrals in accordance with Fubini's theorem:

$$LY = \overline{PSP}_{VUV} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times \left(\int_{SS} SS(\lambda_{scint}) \times d\lambda_{scint} \right) \times \left(\int_{E_{wls}} E_{wls}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PSP_{Vis}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift} \right) \quad (4.46)$$

From equation 4.2, we know that the integral of SS is a known quantity SY:

$$LY = SY \times \overline{PSP}_{VUV} \times \epsilon_{wls} \times \left(\int_{E_{wls}} E_{wls}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PSP_{Vis}(\lambda_{shift}) \times PDE(\lambda_{shift}) \times d\lambda_{shift} \right) \quad (4.47)$$

We must note that the PSP_{Vis} term in the equation 4.47 is a function of f_{sen} , FF_{sys} , $R(\lambda)$, $R_{wall}(\lambda)$, and Q_{Vis} . This equation gives the effective LY for a liquid argon detector described in section 4.2 with no wavelength shifter covering the photosensors. This equation is the basis for a tool developed for performing quick estimations of the LY.

4.6 The Notebook

The analytic model was implemented in the Python programming language as a Jupyter notebook. I chose to write this code in Jupyter environment [99] because of its interactive interface. The major advantage of AMELY is its simplicity due to which the entire code could be implemented in a single notebook. The notebook does data preprocessing, performs AMELY computations, and creates plots. All the plots shown in this chapter were created by this notebook.

The notebook provides an option to choose from two configurations, one where the photosensor is not covered with WLS (default) and a second where the photosensor is covered with WLS. Internally, this is achieved by switching between equations 4.35 and 4.42. The wavelength range for integration is so chosen to include the entire spectrum in which the photosensors are sensitive. If we consider a general case of liquid argon detectors employing TPB or PEN wavelength shifter and DarkSide SiPMs, the wavelength range for integration would be from 366 nm to 560 nm (see figures 4.9c and 4.9a). The Python implementation proved to be quite fast. The entire code is executed in a few seconds.

In order to compute these PSP terms, we need values of R , R_{wall} , E_{wls} etc. In the notebook, one needs to specify which wavelength shifter they want to use: TPB or PEN. The reflectance and emission spectra of PEN and TPB are available to choose from. The emission spectra of PEN was taken from [100]. The WLSE needs to be entered by the user (default=1.0). The default option for photosensor is the DarkSide SiPMs, developed by DarkSide collaboration and FBK based on their NUV-HD-Cryo family of SiPMs [101]. The PDE of these SiPMs is taken from [62]. The reflectance spectra of SiPMs was measured by us (see section 4.7). The absorption and Rayleigh scattering lengths in VUV regime are taken from [102]. The Rayleigh scattering length in visible regime is taken from [95].

These ancillary data files and the notebook are bundled together in the AMELY codebase [103] (see figure 4.7).

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository named 'AMELY' (Private) by user 'sarthchoudhary'. The repository has 89 commits and is currently on the 'main' branch. A table of files and folders is displayed, including .ipynb_checkpoints, data, documents, legacy, notebooks, requirements, results, and README.md. The README file is selected and its content is visible, which includes a statement that it is a clone of the Light Yield Analytic Model repo, and provides links to an Overleaf document, research notes, and other relevant documentations. On the right side, there are sections for 'About', 'Releases', 'Packages', and 'Languages', with 'Languages' showing 'Jupyter Notebook' at 100.0%.

Figure 4.7: Codebase repository for AMELY

4.7 Measurement of Reflectance

I measured the reflectance spectra of DarkSide SiPMs. The reflectance measurements were performed using a Shimadzu UV-3600 spectrophotometer [104] equipped with a 15 cm diameter integrating sphere at the Biological and Chemical Sciences Centre of the University of Warsaw. An integrating sphere is used for collecting the reflected light from the entire sphere. The light beam were incident on the sample at an incidence angle of 7° . The measurement were performed relative to a BaSO_4 standard, which has an absolute reflectance of $98.0 \pm 0.5\%$ in the visible regime.

In order to have large enough SiPM surface area for scan, we glued together SiPM using a black tape (see figure 4.8). The measurement of SiPM reflectance is shown in the figure 4.9b along with the measurements of PEN and TPB performed by other members of our group. I have cross verified the PEN reflectance measurements using a similar instrument available at the Technical University of Munich, Germany. All measurements are performed in air and at room temperature. The further details of this instrument can be found in the section 6.6.1.

Do take a note of oscillations seen in the SiPM reflectance. Such oscillations are produced by interference of reflected light from a multilayered thin film structure, certain Anti-Reflection Coating (ARC) employ such structures [94, 105]. These oscillations indicated that the SiPM's coated with ARC. This finding was quite helpful in getting the simulation correct.

Figure 4.8: SiPM glued to black tape for reflectance measurement.

(a) Emission spectra as function of wavelength for PEN [100] and TPB [106] at cryogenic temperature. Each of the spectra is normalized by their respective maxima.

(b) Reflectance as function of wavelength for DarkSide SiPM, TPB WLSR, and PEN WLSR. The reflectances of TPB and PEN WLSR were measured with the wavelength shifter air-coupled to the ESR. The TPB reflectance has been corrected for the spurious photo-luminescence component described in [106]. All reflectances are at room temperature.

(c) PDE of the DarkSide SiPM at room temperature. Ref [101]

Figure 4.9: Properties of materials in visible spectrum.

Figure 4.10: 2PAC schematic. Ref [70]

4.8 Application to the experimental studies

4.8.1 2PAC: liquid argon test stand for characterization of wavelength shifting reflectors

The 2 Parallel Argon Chambers (2PAC) experiment was designed by our group for performing a definitive comparison between WLSE of PEN and TPB wavelength shifters. With the help of this experiment, it became possible to simultaneously measure the LY of two identical argon cylinders, one using TPB and the other PEN as the wavelength shifter (see figure 4.10). Details of the experimental setup are available in [70]. Both cylindrical detectors are submerged in the same liquid argon volume for a simultaneous measurement, therefore, the comparison between these two wavelength shifters would be independent of argon purity.

I was able to estimate the light yield for this experimental setup using the AMELY notebook. Thus, the AMELY estimates were cross-verified with the MC simulation and the experimental measurements (see figure 4.11). The MC simulation was used to extract the WLSE of PEN and TPB wavelength shifters.

The error% between experimental measurements and AMELY estimates are about 3% and 15% for TPB and PEN, respectively.

(b) Zoomed-in view of the plot above. Also shows the MC predictions and the experimental measurements [70]. The width of the lines comes from the small uncertainty (approx. 1.2%) in coverage fraction of WLSR.

Figure 4.11: LY estimation for 2PAC-like configuration as function of f_{sen}

4.8.2 DWArF: a tonne scale liquid argon experiment

The DarkWave Argon Facility (DWArF) experiment will be discussed in the section 5.4 of chapter 5. The present subsection will discuss the Light Yield estimation made using AMELY.

The original DWArF setup was supposed to have two PMTs: one conventional Visible only PMT and another PTM with visible and VUV sensitivities. The VUV sensitive PMT did not work during the experimental campaign. So far, in the analytic model, there were only two types of surfaces, either those of a photosensor or the wall but, in the case, of DWArF there was a third surface-a dead PMT. The dead PMT would still reflect light but less efficiently than the wall. Similarly, there were patches of surface that could not be covered with WLSR, e.g., the hole through which the manipulator would enter the reflector cage. I had to figure out a way of accounting for this decreased reflectance of the wall.

Consider the equation 4.33, the w term accounts for the photons reflected by the wall. The only difference in the case of DWArF is that the wall is composed of three different component instead of one. Since the number of photons reflected by different parts of the wall, can be added together to calculate the total number of photons reflected by the wall, I can rewrite w as $w_1 + w_2 + w_3$.

Thus, we get

$$PSP_{Vis} = \frac{X}{Q - (s + w_1 + w_2 + w_3)} \quad (4.48)$$

The LY estimate for DWArF is shown in the figure 4.12. The analytic model estimates are consistent with experimental measurement [107] if I use the VUV absorption length of 17 m, which is the value reported, e.g., by ProtoDUNE.

Having said that, the value of VUV absorption length used in the GEANT4 MC simulation that best matched the experimental data was much shorter, at about 60 cm. This, qualitatively, could be possible value given a significant presence of dust in the experimental hall. Setting such a short absorption length was necessary to reproduce the observed LY dependence on the source position, an effect impossible to investigate in the simplified framework of the analytic model.

The reason for this difference is yet to be confirmed. Another hypothesised explanation could be the failure of the GEANT4 model to account for the angular distribution of the wavelength-shifted photons from the reflector and PEN stack in a realistic manner [107].

Figure 4.12: LY estimate as function of f_{sen} in DWArF.

4.9 Future detectors

We used the AMELY notebook for generating predictions for LY for detectors currently under design. Some of these detectors are described in this section.

4.9.1 DarkSide-20k Neutron Veto

A GEANT4 Monte Carlo simulation was developed for the DarkSide-20k neutron veto detector [71] by another member of our group, Dr. Cenk Türkoğlu. The LY for this detector was computed using the MC simulation as well as by the analytic model. Figure 4.13 shows the comparison of LY values computed using these two methods. Thus, the analytic method and the Monte Carlo simulation were used to cross-verify each other. The DarkSide-20k experiment was discussed in the section 2.5. The neutron veto is a cylindrical shell filled with liquid argon.

Remember that other than the L_{char} parameter, AMELY has no way of accounting for geometry or size of the detector. So, I had to find a way to account for this ‘cavity’ in the scintillator volume. I calculated the effective volume of veto by subtracting the TPC volume from the volume of the cylinder.

$$\text{volume of titanium vessel} = V_{TV} = \pi R^2 H + 2 \times \frac{1}{6} \pi h (3a^2 + h^2) \quad (4.49)$$

$$\text{internal surface area of titanium vessel} = S_{TV} = 2\pi RH + 2 \times \pi (a^2 + h^2) \quad (4.50)$$

$$\text{Volume of a regular octagonal prism} = V_{TPC} = 2 \times (1 + \sqrt{2}) \times a^2 \times h \quad (4.51)$$

$$\text{Surface area of a regular octagonal prism} = S_{TPC} = 8 \times a \times h \quad (4.52)$$

$$V_{NV, eff} = V_{TV} - V_{TPC} \quad (4.53)$$

$$S_{NV, eff} = S_{TV} + S_{TPC} \quad (4.54)$$

$$L_{char, eff} = 6 \times \frac{V_{NV, eff}}{S_{NV, eff}} \quad (4.55)$$

The L_{char} value calculated using the equation 4.55 is used for the AMELY calculations. The estimates are shown in the figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13: LY as function of f_{sen} for DarkSide-20k neutron veto: comparison between AMELY and MC simulation results

4.9.2 ARGO

ARGO is a 400 tonne LAr dark matter detector, currently under predesign phase, being planned to reach the ultimate sensitivity to WIMPs. Initially, a single-phase cylindrical geometry with dimensions of 7.05 m in diameter and height is considered. The cylindrical vessel would be made out of acrylic and contain the liquid argon scintillator. For detection of scintillation light, two schemes are considered here: i.) covering the acrylic vessel with a wavelength shifting reflector and using SiPMs sensitive to visible light, or ii.) using VUV sensitive devices without WLSR. One would have to decide how much surface area they want to cover with SiPMs. One could choose to instrument both of the end caps ($f_{sen} = 0.33$) or only one end cap ($f_{sen} = 0.17$). ARGO concept is shown in the figure 4.14.

Figure 4.14: ARGO concept

Case of WLS covered walls

The analytic model LY estimates for ARGO are shown in the figure 4.15. Next, I considered the effect of reduction in the average reflectance of the walls due to inefficiencies in covering the detector walls with WLSR. I use a scaling factor to account for these inefficiencies. The results for the case where detector walls are covered with TPB coated ESR are shown in the figure 4.16.

I also considered how different absorption lengths for VUV in liquid argon would impact the LY. The figure 4.17 shows the LY as function of f_{sen} for different VUV absorption lengths in liquid argon in case the detector walls are covered with TPB coated ESR.

Figure 4.15: LY estimate for ARGO dark matter detector as a function of f_{sen} . Dotted lines are used for the case where SiPM are not covered with wavelength shifters. The solid lines are used for the case where SiPM are covered with WLS. The green lines include the effect of the absorption and Rayleigh scattering on LY whereas red lines do not. Assumed use of DarkSide-20k SiPMs. The measured reflectances of PEN, TPB, and DarkSide SiPMs are used.

Figure 4.16: Effect of reduction in average wall reflectance, R_{wall} on LY, as a function of f_{sen} in ARGO. Three scaling factors are considered for reducing the average wall reflectance. The LAr parameters used are shown on the figure. The calculations are performed for TPB wavelength shifter and DarkSide-20k SiPM. Two sets of calculations are shown: dotted when the SiPM are not coated with TPB and solid lines when the SiPM are also coated with TPB.

Figure 4.17: Effect of the $\lambda_{abs, VUV}$ on LY, as a function of f_{sen} for ARGO

Case of VUV sensitive photosensors

The LCE_{VUV} for VUV sensitive devices can be calculated in this manner:

$$LCE(Q_{VUV}, X_T, s, w) = \frac{X_T}{Q - (s + w)} \quad (4.56)$$

where,

$$X_T = FF_{sys}f_{sen}T$$

T = Transmittance

A = Absorptance

Also,

$$R + T + A = 1 \quad (4.57)$$

The LCE of a single VUV sensitive photosensor can be improved by increasing the transmittance at the liquid argon / silicon interface, where due to its refractive index bare silicon has a fairly high reflectivity. I consider the effect of VUV anti-reflection coatings on VUV-sensitive SiPMs, which can bring such an effect. However, in this case what is a gain for a single SiPM, does not necessarily result in LCE enhancement for the entire large detector. On one hand the anti-reflective coatings increase the LCE of an isolated device, on the other hand they also introduce additional absorption losses, while the reflected photons, in principle, could still have a chance of being detected in another device elsewhere in the detector.

Understanding the global net effect of anti-reflection coatings requires using my model to map the parameter space of various A and R scenarios.

As now there is no WLS in the detector, I instead assumed the constant wall reflectance of 80%, which is the highest value achievable with commercial MgF_2/Al based mirrors.

I show the light yield estimated for the parameter space of $0.2 < R < 0.6$ and $0.0 < A < 0.3$ for $f_{sen} = 0.17$ and $f_{sen} = 1.0$ in the figures 4.18 and 4.19 respectively, informed by parameters of similar coatings reported in the literature.

I consider for full surface coverage with SiPMs ($f_{sen} = 1$), or only one endcap instrumented and the remaining wall otherwise 80% reflective ($f_{sen} = 0.17$).

Summarising the ARGO results, I got LY close to 12 PE/keV projected for full SiPM coverage (reduced to 9 PE/keV with only endcaps instrumented), DarkSide-20k-like SiPMs, TPB-coated ESR reflector and 100 m absorption length. Large, 15-50%, depending on the SiPM coverage fraction, LY drop was observed for the 20 m absorption length.

For VUV sensitive SiPMs combined effect of the SiPM anti-reflection coating reflectivity and absorption was scanned over the practically achievable parameter space (i.e. for full and partial coverage and $\lambda_{abs,VUV}$ of 20 and 100 m, assuming 80% reflectance of walls. LY is approx. 5 PE/keV or less, which can be compared to 10 PE/keV expected in DarkSide-20k.

Figure 4.18: LY estimates for different combinations of SiPM anti-reflective coating absorptance and reflectance for the case when $f_{\text{sen}} = 0.17$. The unit of the colour scale is PE/keV.

Figure 4.19: LY estimates for different combinations of absorptance and reflectance for the case when $f_{\text{sen}} = 1.0$. The unit of the colour scale is PE/keV.

4.9.3 DUNE Far Detector

DUNE [96] is an experiment, currently under construction, to study neutrino oscillations. DUNE will employ large liquid argon detectors to study both the neutrinos generated by a neutrino beam facility at the Fermilab and those generated by supernovae. A light trapping device known as X-ARAPUCA are being planned to be used for detecting scintillation light generated as a result of the neutrino interacting with the argon atoms.

In this section, as an application example, I am using the model to model a rather generic, idealized configuration inspired by the DUNE Horizontal Drift detector design, assuming a cryostat of outer dimensions $65.8 \text{ m} \times 17.8 \text{ m} \times 18.9 \text{ m}$, with four 3.5 m drift volumes are created between five alternating anode and cathode walls, each wall having dimensions of $58 \text{ m} \times 12 \text{ m}$. The standard light collection usually involves sensitive light collection devices, usually coated with a WLS, behind the wire planes [108].

It is proposed to install wavelength-shifter coated reflective surfaces on the cathode, with the possibility of additionally doing the same with the field cage [108]. The main motivation for this would be reducing the energy threshold and in consequence extending the physics reach of DUNE, e.g., to supernova neutrinos.

I will demonstrate the use of the analytic model to estimate light yield for these Far Detector modules using X-ARAPUCA photon detection system. I make use of the equation 4.56 to estimate the light yield in this case. I will use the VUV photon detection efficiency of 2.6% for X-ARAPUCA as quoted in [65]. I assume a VUV reflectance of 50% for the p-Terphenyl (pTP) coated glass window through which light will enter this device. A transmittance of 50% is hinted in the reference [109] for these windows. I assumed that the absorption is negligible, thus, I get a reflectance of 50%. I assumed the SiPMs used in these devices to have performance similar to DarkSide-20k SiPMs, that is, at the shifted wavelength of the WLS bar SiPM will have detection efficiency of about 38%. The estimates are shown in the figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20: LY as function of f_{sen} when the X-ARAPUCA light trapping devices [65] are the sole photon detection device used in the DUNE Far Detector Horizontal Drift module. These estimates do not account for the effect of electric field, which would reduce the scintillation yield.

Predicted light yield is consistent with more detailed Monte Carlo studies, e.g., [110] in the ballpark of 10 pe/MeV for O(1%) photosensor coverage

There is a significant dependence on VUV absorption length, resulting in nearly a one third reduction in LY with absorption and scattering accounted for.

Increasing the WLS efficiency of PEN to bring it closer to TPB is a well motivated way to win a significant amount of light at a manageable cost. Such concepts have been recently started to be pursued by the PoWER and APEX working groups within the DUNE collaboration.

4.9.4 Light Yield Trends

The plot in figure 4.21a shows how the LY of detectors changes with the characteristic length. These calculations do not account for decrease in LY due to the electric field of the Time Project Chambers. As a result, the LY of DUNE Far Detector modules would be less than what is estimated by AMELY.

(a) LY as function of L_{char}

(b) LY as function of L_{char} when the photosensors are also covered with the wavelength shifter

Figure 4.21: LY trend for increasing detector sizes. The plot shows markers with the names of some of the liquid argon detectors for making a comparison between their light yields if the rest of the configuration were the same. These detectors don't necessarily use the configuration shown in the figure.

4.10 Summary

Light Yield (LY) quantifies the amount of scintillation light generated by energy deposition in liquid argon and detected with photosensors. During the design process of a liquid argon detector, estimating LY is immensely useful. However, calculating LY using Monte Carlo simulations is labour-intensive. This chapter presents a handy tool for quickly estimating LY for a given configuration. The analytic model estimates the Light Collection Efficiency (LCE), which can then be used to calculate LY. The pre-existing model has been improved by incorporating the effect of finite reflectances of VUV photons into the formalism.

The model has been implemented in Jupyter Notebook using Python programming language for flexibility. It has been cross-validated against Monte Carlo simulations and experimental data from the 2PAC experiment.

This tool provides quick LY estimations during the detector design phase, supporting design decisions and cross-validating Monte Carlo simulations. It was used to predict LY for the 2PAC, DarkSide-20k neutron veto, and ARGO experiments. The model complements Monte Carlo simulations by offering fast approximations, reducing model development time during the iterative design process. Special cases were also considered, including photosensors covered with wavelength shifters and VUV-sensitive photosensors with anti-reflection coatings.

It was noted that the model benchmarked against GEANT4 Monte Carlo was not able to explain some of the features observed in the DWArF experiment, where the detector size is large enough for absorption to become significant. This discrepancy has not been resolved and requires further investigation with detailed Monte Carlo simulations using different interaction lengths.

Chapter 5

Survey of PEN Wavelength Shifters

This chapter would provide brief overview of PEN wavelength shifters for liquid argon detectors. I will provide a general overview of the experimental method used to measure wavelength-shifting efficiency using liquid argon cryostats. Additionally, I will summarise my contributions to two experimental campaigns focused on the characterisation of PEN wavelength shifters, each lasting four weeks.

5.1 Introduction

While direct Dark matter search experiments (DEAP-3600 [39] and DarkSide-20k [62]) are the central theme of this thesis, the discussion in this chapter applies to all liquid argon detectors. In addition to Direct Dark matter detectors, the notable examples of liquid argon detector include neutrino oscillation experiments (DUNE [96] and MicroBooNE [111]), and experiments searching for neutrino-less double beta decay (LEGEND [63]). Apart from fundamental sciences, these technologies are also being exploited for their potential application in next generation Positron Emission Tomography (PET) scanners [112] and non-invasive monitors for special nuclear materials [113].

As per the discussion earlier, on interaction with ionizing radiation, argon may produce scintillation light in the vacuum ultraviolet regime (128 nm). Such detectors typically use photosensors to detect this scintillation light. Since most commercially available photosensors are not very efficient at these wavelengths, a common scheme employed to efficiently detect argon scintillation light is to first shift these photons to the visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum, where photosensors are more efficient. In the context of radiation detectors, materials which absorb photons of higher energy and emit at lower energies are called **WLS**. In case of liquid argon detectors, the WLS converts UV scintillation photons to visible photons.

These experimental searches will continue to mature and employ increasingly larger detector volumes. Not all aspects of the LAr detectors are easy to scale. Efficiently shifting UV light is one such aspect. Note that we define **WLSE** as the

percentage ratio of number of photons emitted by the WLS to number of photons incident on it. 1,1,4,4-tetraphenyl-1,3-butadiene, or simply, TPB is one of the most popular WLS materials used in a number of experiments. It requires to be vacuum evaporated in order to form a thin film for efficient wavelength shifting [67]. As the detector size increases, the energy and time required to deposit WLS film also increases. Thus, vacuum evaporation becomes inefficient for depositing WLS films for LAr detectors with surface areas of the order 100 m^2 . This prompted the search for an alternative to TPB.

The suitable WLS should have the following properties:

1. scalability to large areas
2. stability in liquid argon throughout the age of detector
3. acceptable WLSE
4. radio purity for low background studies
5. acceptable fluorescence lifetime for efficient use with LAr scintillation

5.2 PEN

Kuźniak et. al. [114] suggested Polyethylene Naphthalate (PEN) as a potential alternative to TPB. Since the PEN is commercially available in the form of sheets, it is much easier to scale than TPB. Further studies by various research groups have established the viability of the same, although each coming up with a different value for WLSE [70, 115, 116]. In a separate study, we undertook an initiative for establishing the long term stability of PEN in liquid argon [107, 117]. The radioactivity of PEN has been shown to be within acceptable limits [118]. In this chapter, we will discuss the characterization of fluorescence properties of different variants of commercial PEN. Chapter 6 will discuss Quality Assurance of the commercially procured PEN for DarkSide-20k veto detector.

Figure 5.1: Skeletal diagram for poly(ethylene 2,6-naphthalate), or PEN for short. PEN is a polyester closely related to polyethylene terephthalate (PET).

5.3 Optimisation of light collection with PEN

We undertook a dedicated campaign to study and find the optimal PEN based WLSR. We performed measurements of WLSE of different grades of PEN available in the market, in combination with various reflectors.

We performed liquid argon measurements with a number of samples in combination with different reflectors. The choice of reflectors is Tetrarex (TTX), ESR, and Tyvek. Commercially procured grades of PEN used in these measurements are Q51 and Q53. We also performed some measurements with sanded PEN samples. The sanding was performed either with a sandpaper of grit P240 or P500. Some of the samples were hand sanded, while some were sanded with help of a handheld sanding machine. The combination of reflector, PEN grade, and sanding technique used for each measurement are listed in the table 5.1. Figure 5.2d shows a photograph of a sanded sample of PEN.

5.3.1 Measurement of WLSE with LArS

A reliable method for determining wavelength shifting efficiency of PEN is by measuring its visible light emission in liquid argon. It was possible to do just that at the University of Zurich (UZH) using the Liquid Argon Setup (LArS) (see figure 5.2).

The process works as follows: The wavelength shifting sample is wrapped around a cylindrical sample holder, which is placed inside a cryostat. Once the cryostat is sealed, it is pumped to vacuum. Then, the cryostat is filled with gaseous argon. Afterwards, we turn on the flow of liquid nitrogen through copper coils, which provides the cooling for liquefaction of argon.

An alpha emitter, e.g., ^{241}Am , is attached to the sample holder. It produces alpha particles that cause liquid argon to scintillate, generating VUV photons. Some of these photons reach the WLS and undergo shifting.

To ensure uniform light collection, the alpha source is positioned at the bottom centre of the sample holder, with the PMT placed at the top centre. The PMT detects the shifted photons and has some sensitivity to VUV photons as well.

(a) LArS exterior

(b) LArS interior. A reflector + PEN stack wrapped around the sample holder is visible in this photograph.

(c) LArS schematic. Image source: [116]

(d) A sanded PEN Q53 125 μm sample

Figure 5.2: Measurement of WLSE with LArS

Table 5.1: LArS measurements

ID	Reflector	WLS	Sanding	Note
M1	Absorber	-	-	Absorber
M2	TTX	Q53 25um	P500 machine	-
M3	TTX	Q51 50um	P240 hand	WLS on exterior (Discarded)
M4	TTX	Q53 125um	P500 machine	-
M5	TTX	Q53 125um	smooth	-
M6	TTX	Q53 125um	P240 hand	-
M7	ESR	Q53 125um	smooth	-
M8	TTX	Q53 125um	smooth	Repeats M5; underpressure
M9	Aluminium	Q53 25um	P240 hand	PEN is laminated on Al
M10	Tyvek	Q53 25um	smooth	PEN glued to Tyvek

5.3.2 Data Analysis: Triplet Lifetime Estimation

Triplet lifetime is essential for assessing the purity of argon for the run, and making corrections to the estimated light yield.

I wrote a Python program to stack (adding waveforms bin-by-bin) all waveforms in a run. Then, I remove the pre-trigger waveform (truncation) and shift the waveform. Finally, I fit an exponential function to this truncated shifted waveform (see figure 5.3). This procedure is repeated for all runs. The results obtained from these fits are shown in the table 5.2. The table only shows the mean lifetime for one run per measurement. The figure 5.4 summarises these results.

Figure 5.3: stacking all waveform in each run. An exponential function is fit to this shifted truncated waveform.

Table 5.2: Abridged table of estimated mean triplet lifetime for LArS measurements

Measurement	Run	Mean Life Time [μ s]
M1	R33_0	0.99
M2	R6_3	1.15
M3	R0_0	1.12
M4	R1_1	1.11
M5	R1_0	1.06
M6	R1_1	1.07
M7	R1_1	0.99
M8	R3_3	0.95
M9	R1_1	1.08
M10	R1_5	0.94

Figure 5.4: Summary of LArS measurements. Ref [119]

5.4 Test of PEN stability in liquid argon with DWArF

DWArF, contrary to its name, is a fairly large-size experiment. In my knowledge, it uses the largest volume of argon with which PEN has been used as a wavelength shifter fully covering the detector walls, as yet. It contains approximately 1.4 tonne of liquid argon. The main goal of DWArF campaign was to demonstrate the stability of PEN foils in a relatively large cryostat for a couple of weeks. DWArF employed nearly 4 m² of PEN sheets for this purpose. Our team member, Maciej Kuźwa, designed a reflector cage (figure 5.5c) to hold the PEN sheets and ESR foils, so that, these could be submerged in liquid argon. The cage is a regular hexagonal prism with side approximately 0.50 m and height approximately 1.01 m. The cage was composed of frame bars and metallic rods. We did a test assembly of the reflector cage in Warsaw before taking the material to CERN (figure 5.5b). The ESR sheets available in large format come with an adhesive attached to it. We used toluene to remove the adhesive layer from ESR sheets, following the procedure developed for this purpose by the GERDA collaboration (for use in a liquid argon veto surrounding their high purity germanium counters used for the neutrinoless double beta decay search). I confirmed that it was easier to remove adhesive with Toluene as compared to isopropyl alcohol.

The functional aspect of DWArF is pretty similar to that of LArS. A radioactive alpha source is placed at an ‘L’ shaped manipulator arm. This arm can be moved vertically or rotated horizontally within $\pm 50^\circ$. The PMT on top is sensitive only to the visible emission from WLS.

We assembled the setup in Building 182 at CERN, which took about a week because of a large number of vacuum fittings and feedthroughs that had to be installed on the lid of the dewar in order to properly instrument the system. The assembly took place on a separate stand beside the tank. Afterwards, the PMTs were connected to High Voltage (HV) power supply and DAQ. Finally, the lid, with the reflector cage and the alpha source manipulator suspended underneath, was craned into the dewar, as shown in figure 5.6. The dewar was sealed and filled with high purity (6N) liquid argon. The cryostat vessel is surrounded by a hollow insulator jacket that needs to be pumped to vacuum. The vacuum provides insulation to the main vessel. Building 182 has a liquid argon supply line connected to a reservoir tank outside the building. Thus, we could directly fill the dewar with liquid argon.

Following first calibration data taken post-fill, we experienced a sudden failure of the DAQ system available in the lab, and had to switch to taking data with an oscilloscope, while waiting for our collaborators to bring a replacement DAQ from UZH.

I spent nearly a month at CERN during that experimental campaign, longer than any other team member external to CERN. In addition to participation in the assembly, my role during regular data taking shifts was operating the system and starting runs for various configurations of the PMT voltage and alpha manipulator position. In addition to this, every 3 to 5 days the dewar had to be topped up with liquid argon in order to compensate for the boil-off and keep the PMT submerged. Last but not the least, together with other team members, I regularly monitored the

(a) DWArF Schematic. Source: [119]

(b) Reflector cage test assembly at CEZAMAT, Warsaw

(c) DWArF CAD design

(d) Photograph of reflector cage inside the dewar

Figure 5.5: DWArF setup

pressure in the tank within prescribed safe limits, adjusting the relief valve as needed.

The data collected as a result of this measurement campaign was analysed by our collaborators, Vikas Gupta and Prof Tina Pollmann. They found that the argon purity was stable during the measurement campaign and the triplet lifetime is around 1.3-1.4 μs . They also found the data to be consistent with 40-70% WLSE (informed by simulations). The figure 5.7 shows the evolution of triplet lifetime and light yield with time.

Figure 5.6: Photograph showing different segments of DWArF. This photograph was taken right before the reflector cage was craned into the dewar.

Figure 5.7: Time evolution of mean triplet lifetime and light yield for the DWArF experiment. Ref [107]

5.5 Summary

Wavelength shifters are essential for efficient detection of argon scintillation light. However, the scalability of wavelength shifters becomes a concern for large scale detectors with more than 100 m^2 of surface area. This chapter presents a brief overview of the Polyethylene Naphthalate (PEN) wavelength shifters for liquid argon detectors.

I present an experimental campaign in which we studied the wavelength-shifting efficiencies of various commercially available grades of PEN in combination with different reflectors. We tested these PEN-based wavelength-shifting reflectors in liquid argon, using argon scintillation light as an excitation source to drive PEN fluorescence. I also discuss an experiment designed to demonstrate the long-term stability of PEN wavelength shifters in liquid argon. It has been shown that the experimental setup using PEN maintains a consistent light yield over a period of two weeks.

Chapter 6

Quality Assessment of PEN wavelength shifters

In the Chapter 5, I discussed the ongoing efforts for developing scalable wavelength shifters for large scale LAr detectors. In the present chapter, I will demonstrate the WLSE measuring capabilities of a tabletop setup for measurement of wavelength shifting efficiency of PEN sheets. So far, we have seen the use of various liquid argon setups for measurement of WLSE of PEN. In this chapter I will introduce a slightly different technique using gaseous argon. Working with gaseous argon is easier and faster, as it removes the additional step of liquefaction. This approach greatly simplifies the measurement workflow and speeds up the whole process. This is advantageous as this setup is going to be used in a campaign for the quality assessment of PEN sheets for the DarkSide-20k veto detectors, which constitutes a fairly large number of measurements.

6.1 Introduction

PEN is available commercially in form of sheets. Rolls of PEN sheet have been procured for use in construction of DarkSide-20k veto detectors (figure 6.1). One issue we face with commercial PEN is that different batches of PEN seem to have different WLSE. Additionally, we want to test the uniformity of WLSE of PEN from the same the roll. We want to ensure that the WLSE of PEN sheets should not vary along either of the dimensions. For this reason, we want to exercise strict quality control over PEN sheets, we will measure the WLSE of a PEN sample from each batch before they go for installation in the veto detectors. For this purpose, we will be using a custom setup recently developed in collaboration with the National Center for Nuclear Research, Świerk [120]. We have designated this experimental setup as Argon Gas Setup (ArGSet) [121].

Figure 6.1: A roll of PEN Q51 25 μm sheet. Annotations I, II, and III show the location of sample extraction.

6.2 ArGSet: Argon Gas Setup

The Argon Gas Setup (ArGSet) consists of a cryostat containing a sample holder, an ^{241}Am alpha source and two Hamamatsu S14160-6050HS SiPMs [122]. The SiPMs (figure 6.4c) sit on a Boron Nitride ceramic [123] base which is connected to a copper baseplate which is connected to the copper cold-finger. The aluminium sample holder (figure 6.4d) is also connected to the cold-finger. Thus, both WLS and the SiPMs will be at cryogenic temperature once thermal equilibrium is achieved. For the measurements, the inner vacuum-insulated chamber of the cryostat will be flushed with Argon gas and sealed off. The ^{241}Am emits 5.486 MeV alphas. The alpha will scintillate the argon gas, and this scintillation will illuminate the WLS sample. The SiPMs will be facing the sample to detect the fluorescence from WLS (figure 6.4a). Figure 6.4b shows the inner chamber with the attached sample holder. The setup is also equipped with a temperature sensor. Figure 6.2 shows the setup connected to an oscilloscope.

Figure 6.2: ArGSet connected to an oscilloscope at NCBJ

Figure 6.3: ArGSet connected to DAQ at CEZAMAT

Operation: Once the sample is loaded in the sample holder, the setup is closed followed by the Argon purge of the inner chamber. Afterwards, the outer chamber is vacuumed to 10^{-5} mbar. Before performing any measurements, the cold finger is immersed in a liquid nitrogen dewar for cool down. The equilibrium is achieved in about 5 to 6 hours.

Data Acquisition: SiPM signals need an external amplifier. The output of this amplifier is then fed to a CAEN V1725SB digitizer [124]. The digitizer samples at the rate of 1 sample per 4 ns. The digitized pulses are sent to a linux computer, where data acquisition is done with Midas software [125]. Midas writes waveforms along with metadata in a Midas specific binary file format. Each SiPM is read separately, and its output is written separately as an independent channel. The two SiPM signals are also summed on with the electronics circuit before being sent to the digitizer. This third signal is then read separately as an independent channel. Thus, there are three channels: one for each SiPM (channel 1 & 2) and another (channel 0) for the summed output. The summed output is the analogue addition of the signals from two SiPMs with an additional amplification factor of 5.

(a) Schematic

(b) Inner chamber separated

(c) SiPMs

(d) Loaded sample holder

(e) Next to a ruler for comparison

(f) inner chamber closed

Figure 6.4: ArGSet inner chamber

6.3 ArGSet SiPM Calibration: Gain Balancing

Firstly, I want to ensure that both SiPMs give same amount of charge for same number of incident photons. For this, I need to operate the SiPMs on the same voltage above their respective breakdown voltages. The voltage above breakdown voltage is also known as Over-Voltage (OV). I had to find the OV for each SiPM.

This is achieved in the following manner: The inner chamber is not closed and instead SiPMs are operated in vacuum. The light port to ArGSet is kept open to allow ambient light to enter the system and LED pulser is not used either. SiPM's are connected to the CAEN power supply. The voltage to each SiPM is increased in small steps until a positive current starts flowing. A CSV file is used for writing down the voltage and current values. The voltage is increased initially in steps of 5 V but kept reducing the step size as the current shoot up. The Voltage-Current (VI) curve for both SiPM is shown in the Fig 6.5a. I fit a straight line to each VI curve in the vicinity of the breakdown. Then used the resulting fit parameters to find the breakdown voltage, i.e., voltage corresponding to current = $-1 \mu A$. A zoomed-in section of the VI curves is shown in the figure 6.5b. The fits to VI curves and breakdown voltages found from these fits are also shown in the figure 6.5b. The breakdown voltages are listed in the table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Breakdown voltages for SiPMs

SiPM-1	SiPM-2
$29.19 \pm 0.06 \text{ V}$	$29.67 \pm 0.06 \text{ V}$

6.4 ArGSet SiPM Calibration: Photo-Electron Spectrum

We want to translate the collected charge to number of Photo-Electron (PE), for this we need to perform sPE calibration.

We do this using a 400 nm pulsed LED source [126] which is capable of driving 8 ns pulses. We take data in a controlled manner:

- i. Take LED data without placing any sample.
- ii. Repeat this over several runs with differing LED intensity.

This data was used for creating PE charge spectrum. Since distinct peaks were not visible in these plots, I wrote a code [127] for removing noisy events. This program makes use of Pyreco software library [128] developed by DarkSide collaboration. The workflow for generating PE charge spectrum is explained in the following subsection.

6.4.1 Calibration workflow

This is an overview of different steps in the workflow:

(a) VI curve

(b) linear fit to the VI curve

Figure 6.5: Voltage-Current Curve

- I. **Format conversion** (purple blocks): First, the Midas file is converted to a Python pickle file [129]. Pyreco has the tools needed for reading Midas files. My code makes use of Pyreco for reading the waveforms as NumPy arrays [130], then adds them to a Pandas DataFrame [131], and saves the DataFrame object as pickle file to the disk. Only the waveforms are kept discarding all metadata. Some of the Midas files contain empty waveforms. This step discards such waveforms. I am calling the resultant DataFrame as event catalogue.

- II. **Clean waveform search** (green section): In order to reject all noisy events, I use a very strict condition for accepting an event as a clean event: I discard events which seem to have anything other than a single SiPM pulse. The way I implemented this is by making use of Pyreco's Auto-Recursive Moving-Average (AR-MA) filter [132]. The waveforms which are found to be clean are then added to a DataFrame. I call this DataFrame as the clean catalogue.

 Note: Pyreco models an ideal SiPM pulse as a function with two components, a Gaussian for the fast rising component and an exponential for the slow decaying component (see equation 6.1). The Auto-Recursive function works as a filter, and computes the exponential from the raw waveform while Moving-Average is used to compute the Gaussian component. The term 'AR-MA filter' is terminology specific to Pyreco and should not be confused with ARIMA (or ARMA) models used for time series analysis.

- III. **SiPM pulse model fitting** (red section): The AR-MA filter used in the previous step is by-default tuned for the SiPMs produced for use in DarkSide-20k. We use different SiPM in ArGSet. Therefore, I need to retune the AR-MA filter. I need the pulse parameters of ArGSet SiPMs. To do this, I use a pulse template as shown by equation 6.1. I loop over all the clean events and fit the pulse template with each of them. The events which do not fail the fit are added to a DataFrame called the fit catalogue.

- IV. **Pulse parameter extraction**: I will construct distributions of the model parameters obtained in the previous step. I can then extract the mean and standard deviation values from these distributions.

- V. **Retuning AR-MA**: I use the parameters found in the last step to retune the AR-MA filter. Then, reapply the clean event search algorithm. The clean catalogue is then passed through the template fitting step. The fit catalogue thus generated is passed to next step.

- VI. **PE charge spectrum** (yellow section): Get AR-MA filtered waveforms from the fit catalogue. These waveforms are integrated to obtain ADC charge values. I then histogram these charges values to create the PE charge spectrum.

The workflow is depicted as a flowchart in the figure 6.6. The symbols have usual meaning.

Figure 6.6: Workflow for creating PE charge spectrum. The workflow is divided amongst two Python scripts and one Jupyter notebook. In the digital version, this diagram is best viewed at 150% zoom.

The steps II-VI are summarised below.

Step II: Algorithm for clean event search

- II. I need a collection of clean events from which I can find the pulse parameter values. I will first use AR-MA filter with the default parameters. I will update these parameters in a later step and reapply this algorithm for generating the PE charge spectrum. For now, the algorithm is used only to drive the pulse parameters. This algorithm is taken from Ref. [132].
- (a) First, the AR-MA filter is applied to each channel.
 - (b) Then I take Moving Average (MA) of the AR-MA filtered waveforms.
 - (c) Then I subtract the MA array from the AR-MA filtered waveform. These resultant arrays are then passed to the next step.
 - (d) For each subtracted array, the negative samples will be replaced with zero.
 - (e) Then I take Root Mean Square (RMS) of these arrays. In each resultant array, samples less than 3 times the RMS will be replaced by zero.
 - (f) A peak search algorithm [133] will be used to find the number of peaks in the resultant arrays.
 - (g) If the number of peaks from previous steps is not equal to one, the event is rejected.
 - (h) The events for which the number of peaks is equal to one are added to a DataFrame called the clean catalogue.

The peaks can be extracted as shown in the figure 6.7.

Step III: SiPM pulse model fitting

- (a) For each event in the clean catalogue, I fit the SiPM pulse model with the waveforms. The SiPM pulse model is a combination of a Gaussian function (the fast component) and an exponential function (the slow component) as shown in equation 6.1.

$$A(t) = (1 - \alpha) \cdot G(t - t_0) + \alpha \cdot \text{heaviside}(t - t_0) \cdot \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{t - t_0}{\tau}\right)}{\tau} \quad (6.1)$$

where, Gaussian function G is given by

$$G(t_0, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(t - t_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (6.2)$$

And, $A(t)$ is the pulse amplitude, α is a dimensionless scaling constant, t_0 is the time at which exponential decay starts, τ is the time constant for the exponential function, and σ is the standard deviation of the Gaussian

Figure 6.7: Demonstration of AR-MA filter on an example event to find signal amidst noise. The top plot shows the raw waveform. The subsequent plots show the effect of steps II. a to e. The plot d shows several smaller peaks. Setting the threshold at $3 \times \text{RMS}$ in the step (e) removes most of the smaller peaks from appearing in the bottom most plot. Then the peak detect algorithm can be used to find the number and position of peaks. Each bin is 4 ns long.

function. The figure 6.8 show a raw waveform recorded in channel 0 and the SiPM model fit.

Figure 6.8: LED pulse recorded on channel 0 and the SiPM pulse model fit

- (b) The events for which the fit does not converge are discarded. The rest of the events are added to a DataFrame called fit catalogue.
- (c) The fit parameters obtained are catalogued in the fit catalogue. The clean event search and SiPM pulse model fitting is handled by a Python script.

Step IV: Pulse parameter value extraction

III. Once the fit catalogue is created, the Python script exits. The further processing requires a more interactive approach, therefore, I decided to do it in a jupyter notebook. The notebook reads the fit catalogue files. It can also perform concatenation on several fit catalogues for different runs so that I can gather sufficient statistics.

- (a) I will first create 1D histograms for each SiPM pulse model parameter. Thus, I will have three histograms, one for each parameter: σ , τ , and α .
- (b) I also plot the distribution as a function of two parameters.
- (c) I find that the ' α vs σ ' distribution has two distinct event populations in channel number 2 as can be seen from the figure 6.9. This behaviour is unique to channel 2. There is no sign of a distinct population in channel 0 as evident from the figure 6.10.

Figure 6.10: α vs σ plot for channel 0

- (d) On investigation, the second smaller cluster of events was deemed a noisy feature. Figure 6.11 shows comparison between a typical event from the main population and the events from the secondary population, i.e., the outliers.

Figure 6.11: Outliers selected from α vs σ plot

- (e) I used a rectangular cut (red box in figure 6.9) to remove the smaller cluster of events.
- (f) The 1D distributions were then fitted with Gaussian and I obtained the mean and standard deviation of these parameters. The figures 6.12, 6.13, and 6.14 show the Gaussian fits to histograms of σ , τ , and α respectively. Histograms are shown only for channel 0.

Figure 6.12: Histogram of σ values of events in channel 0

Figure 6.13: Histogram of τ values of events in channel 0

Figure 6.14: Histogram of α values of events in channel 0

Step V: Retuning AR-MA

IV. Now, I do have the pulse parameters to retune the AR-MA filter for ArGSet SiPMs.

- I will manually update AR-MA filter parameters using the mean values of pulse parameters obtained in the previous step.
- Now, I will repeat the step II, i.e., clean waveform search. The clean catalogue thus obtained is passed to the next step for generating the PE charge spectrum.

Step VI: PE charge spectrum

V. In this step, I will use the event catalogue from the previous step for generating the PE charge spectrum. The same notebook which was used for extracting parameter values has the code for generating PE charge spectrum.

- (a) I apply the AR filter to each waveform in the entire fit catalogue. AR filter can be mathematically expressed by the following equation:
- (b) I use a windowed integrating function on the resultant arrays. The array values falling within the window are summed to obtain the ADC charge values. The size of the window is fixed throughout this exercise. However, the location of the window is dynamic. The window starts 112 samples before the peak to 112 samples after the peak. The peak location is the same as determined by the peakdetect algorithm in step II (d).
- (c) I then histogram these charges values to create the PE charge spectrum.
- (d) Since the pulse parameters are different for different channels. I repeat steps through III to VI for all three channels separately.

The resultant PE charge spectrum, colloquially known as a fingerplot is shown in the figure 6.15.

Figure 6.15: PE charge spectrum for channel 0

6.4.2 single PE calibration

I will extract the sPE charge from this PE charge spectrum. The peak in the PE charge spectrum correspond to number of Photo Electrons collected. The first peak represents 1 Photo-Electron, the second peak represents 2 Photo-Electrons, and so on. The sPE charge was estimated using the following steps:

1. I fit the first two prominent peaks with a Gaussian function.
2. Since the first peak is suppressed as a result of event rejection by the ArGSet noise rejection algorithm, I will use the next two peaks for this purpose.

3. Thus, I find the mean charge for 2 PE and 3 PE peaks with the help of Gaussian fits as shown in the figure 6.16.

Figure 6.16: Gaussian fits to PE peaks

From the fits, I get

$$\bar{Q}_{3PE,0} = 4859.6 \pm 12.3$$

$$\bar{Q}_{2PE,0} = 3246.7 \pm 7.3$$

4. The difference between the charge values of any two adjust peaks would be the same as that of a single PE.

$$\bar{Q}_{sPE,0} = \bar{Q}_{3PE,0} - \bar{Q}_{2PE,0}$$

$$\bar{Q}_{sPE,0} = 4859.6 - 3246.7$$

$$\bar{Q}_{sPE,0} = 1612.8$$

I can also calculate the standard deviation for sPE using error propagation:

$$\epsilon_{sPE,0} = \sqrt{(\epsilon_{3PE,0})^2 + (\epsilon_{2PE,0})^2}$$

$$\epsilon_{sPE,0} = \sqrt{(12.30)^2 + (7.25)^2}$$

$$\epsilon_{sPE,0} = 14.3$$

Finally,

$$\bar{Q}_{sPE,0} = 1612.8 \pm 14.3 \quad (6.3)$$

The sPE charge calculation is shown only for channel 0. I can repeat the above procedure for any channel.

6.4.3 SNR

I use the following definition of Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), which is taken from Ref [134]:

$$SNR = \frac{\overline{Q_{sPE}}}{\sigma_{pedestal}} \quad (6.4)$$

The signal clean-up workflow removes the pedestal, but the $\sigma_{pedestal}$ can be calculated from the pre-cleaned up AR-MA filtered waveforms available in the event catalogue. The figure 6.17 shows a histogram of integrated charge in the pretrigger window. I fit a Gauss function to this histogram. I use the standard deviation found from this fit in the equation 6.4 to calculate the SNR for the analogue summation channel.

Figure 6.17: Integrated charge in pretrigger window. The statistics are higher in this plot as this dataset contains events which are not considered clean, and the majority of these will be removed by the clean-up workflow.

$$SNR = \frac{1613}{794}$$

$$SNR \approx 2.0$$

ArGCAT: ArGSet Calibration and Analysis Tools

The tools for data analysis and SiPM calibration are bundled in a codebase [127]:

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository for ArGSet. The repository name is 'ArGSet' and it has 0 stars and 0 forks. The current branch is 'main' and the commit hash is '30a58073'. The commit message is 'cosmetic changes to the plot' by Sarthak Choudhary, authored 6 days ago. The repository contains several folders and files, with the most recent commit being 'update to README.md' 3 months ago.

Name	Last commit	Last update
CAENAnalyzer	notebook for reading CAEN digitizer out...	10 months ago
Legacy	Reorganized repo. Moved redundant co...	5 months ago
conda_env_specifications	repo re-organization	3 months ago
config_files	pyreco config file for channel zero	3 months ago
notebooks	cosmetic changes to the plot	6 days ago
results	added an extra data point for the Windo...	3 months ago
scripts	file renamed	2 months ago
src	only using AR filtered wf	2 months ago
util	script for counting total number of even...	5 months ago
.gitattributes	update to git attributes file	3 months ago
.gitignore	Revert "update to gitignore"	3 months ago
README.md	update to README	3 months ago

Project information: ArGSet revived. 108 Commits, 3 Branches, 2 Tags, 3.8 MiB Project Storage. README, Add LICENSE, Add CHANGELOG, Add CONTRIBUTING, Add Kubernetes cluster, Set up CI/CD, Add Wiki, Configure Integrations. Created on May 30, 2024.

Figure 6.18: ArGSet calibration and analysis tools

6.5 Cryogenic Measurements with ArGSet

Once the setup was calibrated, we used it for measurements of PEN and TPB samples. The procedure for operating the setup was described in the section 6.2. This time, we load either a TPB or a PEN sample in the sample holder, and fill the chamber with argon gas (6N purity). The TPB is coated on an ESR foil. The PEN samples were also backed by an ESR foil. The LED pulser is not used for data taking during the measurement runs. Since there is going to be more light in the chamber, we increase the length of events from 1750 samples to 4000 samples. Each sample is 4 ns long. The figure 6.19 shows a waveform recorded when a PEN sample was loaded in the sample holder ring.

Figure 6.19: Raw waveform taken with a PEN sample. Each bin is 4 ns long.

6.5.1 Thermal stability

It was observed that the integrated charge (the sum of raw waveforms) drifts over time (see figure 6.20), following the gradual warm-up of the setup. Therefore, we only use a range of collected events.

The grey vertical lines shown in the figure indicate the event range used for analysis. Throughout the following discussion, whenever I refer to the ‘full run,’ I mean the range between the grey lines.

The Resistance Temperature Detector was identified as one of the main sources of noise. Therefore, it was only used at the beginning and at the end of each run. The temperature for the present measurement was $-167.01\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the beginning and $-171.20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the end of the measurement. Note that the temperature would have been lower for the range selected.

Figure 6.20: Time evolution of integrated charge (\propto the amount of detected photons) in the analogue sum channel. Grey vertical lines indicate the event range selected for analysis. This event range is equivalent to approx. 12 hours of measurement. The second peak corresponds to topping up of the cold finger liquid nitrogen reservoir.

6.5.2 Analysis

I will discuss the method used for the analysis of data collected during the measurement runs. I implemented the entire analysis procedure in a Python script. The paths to directories containing the Midas data files, event catalogues, and the output folder are specified separately in a YAML file.

Event selection

Event selection was based on the following event selection cuts:

- i. **1st cut**: This cut uses the sum of pre-trigger window for selecting events. The purpose of this cut is to remove events where the SiPM might not have had the time to fully discharge before the next pulse arrived. Pre-trigger window is defined to be consisted of first 350 samples in a waveform. This corresponds to the first $1.4 \mu\text{s}$ of an event. The threshold for pre-trigger sum is found in this

manner: first calculate pre-trigger sum for all the events in the event catalogue. Make a histogram of these pre-trigger sum values separately for each channel; see figure 6.21. Now, I find the threshold based on where histogram has a very sharp decline. The pre-trigger sum values higher than this value are outliers. For the PEN measurement run, I get threshold for channel-0 = 4000. The pre-trigger cut used pre-trigger sum values of channel-0 alone.

Figure 6.21: Histogram of Pre-trigger sum values

- ii. **2nd cut**: This cut is based on the Center of Mass (COM) of the waveform. This cut ensures that only the genuine argon scintillation pulses are used for analysis. COM is defined by equation 6.5

$$\text{COM} = \frac{\sum_i A_i \cdot i}{\sum_i i} \quad (6.5)$$

where A_i is the waveform amplitude of the i_{th} time bin. The COM cut works in this manner: first calculate COM for all events surviving the previous cut. Make a histogram of these COM values for each channel (fig 6.22). Fit a Gaussian function to these distributions. From these fits, we obtain the mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ). Now, I base the cut on this criterion that an event

would be selected only if the COM of that event lies within $\mu \pm p \times \sigma$. The COM cut used COM of channel-1 alone. For the PEN measurement run, I determined p to be 2.

Figure 6.22: Histogram of COM values

- iii. **3rd cut:** This cut rejects the event if the time separation between pulses in channel-1 and channel-2 exceeds a threshold. The purpose of this cut is to remove events where the two SiPMs might be collecting photons from two different events that happen to occur nearly simultaneously, or light reaching from an earlier event. The pulse difference threshold is found in this manner: first calculate the difference between maxima peak positions for channel-1 and channel-2 waveforms for an event, and then repeat the procedure for all events surviving the previous cuts. Make a histogram of these pulse difference values. I find the threshold based on where histogram has a very sharp decline. I found that the thresholds determined by this method were not effective. I had to adjust this threshold by inspection. For the PEN measurement run, I used threshold = 40.

Figure 6.23: Histogram of maximum difference between the pulse position in channels 1 and 2

The figure 6.24 shows the effect of each successive cut on the charge distribution. The figure 6.26 shows the overall effect of event selection cuts on all channels.

Figure 6.24: The effect of event selection cuts on charge distribution. The bottom panel shows the cut efficiency.

6.5.3 Argon triplet mean lifetime

The estimation of mean lifetime is very important as it can be used to assess the argon purity. The mean lifetime is obtained by fitting an appropriate scintillation pulse function with the stacked waveform. The procedure is straight forward:

- i. Apply [AR-MA](#) filter to all the waveforms that survive event selection cuts.
- ii. Stack the filtered waveforms for each channel. Stacking is performed by addition of waveform amplitudes in respective time bins.
- iii. Then, truncate the stacked filtered waveform to remove the pre-trigger window. Then shift the resultant waveform. This shifted truncated waveform is used for fitting.
- iv. I employ the scintillation pulse function given in equation [6.6](#) for fitting. The parameters τ_3 and τ_1 give the time constant for the slow and fast component of the scintillation pulse, respectively.

$$f_1(x) = a_3 e^{-(x-a_0)/\tau_3} + a_1 e^{-(x-a_0)/\tau_1} \quad (6.6)$$

- v. The portion of waveform to be used in fit is chosen so that I can capture both the fast as well the slow components. Fit range is also influenced by the value of chi-square metric of the fit. I want to get as good a fit as possible.

I can calculate the mean lifetime for the entire measurement run as well as parts of the run. By calculating mean lifetime for a part of the run, we can assess if the argon purity changes during the measurement run. The figure [6.25a](#) shows the fit to the stacked waveforms for a PEN measurement run.

The triplet lifetime found from fit is 3.06 ± 0.16 (syst.) μs . The value of triplet lifetime stated in literature varies from 2.8 to 3.2 μs [[135](#)].

The figure [6.25b](#) shows the evolution of triplet lifetime over time.

(a) Fits to stacked waveforms for entire run. Mean argon triplet lifetime (τ_3) is extracted from the fits.

(b) Mean lifetime for parts of the run: I divide the run into 5 equal parts and then calculate the mean triplet lifetime for each part. Evolution of triplet lifetime helps to understand how argon purity is changing over time. Since the lifetime does not drop significantly over time, it can be concluded that argon purity does not change significantly over time. The 5th part shows abnormal mean lifetime for channels 1, which remains unexplained.

Figure 6.25: Argon triplet mean lifetime

6.5.4 Measured charge

I calculate the collected charge in ADC units by taking summation over the entire waveform for all events, separately for each channel. Figure 6.26 shows the comparison of charge distributions before and after applying the event selection cuts for the PEN run.

I then fit a Gaussian function to the charge distribution for each channel, as shown on the right side column of the figure 6.26. I can extract the mean charge from these fits.

Figure 6.26: Charge distribution

Number of photoelectrons

To calculate the number of photoelectrons detected in a channel, I can divide the total charge collected by the single PE charge.

$$N_{PE} = \frac{\overline{Q_{integral}}}{Q_{sPE}} \quad (6.7)$$

The table 6.2 lists the mean value of charge collected, and the number of photoelectrons estimated from that charge value.

Table 6.2: Number of detected photoelectrons

	Ch-0
Mean Integral Charge [4ns.ADC units]	5.184e+05
sPE charge [4ns.ADC units]	1612.84
Photoelectrons N_{pe}	321

Asymmetry

It was observed that the charge collected by the two SiPMs varies despite having already calibrated the gain. We use the metric $X_{Asymmetry}$ defined by the equation 6.8.

$$X_{asym} = \frac{\text{peak}_1 - \text{peak}_2}{\text{peak}_1 + \text{peak}_2} \quad (6.8)$$

This is likely a result of the geometrical asymmetry of SiPMs with respect to the sample. X_{asym} is shown in the first plot on the right side column of the figure 6.26.

It has been observed that the $X_{Asymmetry}$ changes from run to run. This is likely due to the variation in argon pressure in different measurement runs.

6.6 Room Temperature Measurements with Spectrophotometer

This section reports on the fluorescence measurement performed at Room Temperature (RT) using a spectrophotometer. This technique has previously been used in [114] to investigate the wavelength shifting properties of PEN. In the subsections that will follow, I will attempt to shed some light on the consistency of WLSE of various PEN samples. I will extract the measurement at 190 nm from these measurements and use these as proxy measure of the wavelength shifting efficiency at 128 nm.

6.6.1 Spectrophotometer

These measurements were performed using a Shimadzu UV-3600 spectrophotometer [104] available at the Biological and Chemical Sciences Centre of the University of Warsaw.

The general operational scheme of a spectrophotometer is explained in brief: a diffraction grating or prism is used to disperse the light from a stable light source(s). The selected wavelength range $\Delta\lambda$ is then split into two beams, namely, the reference beam and the sample beam. The reference beam is fed to photosensor without interaction with medium other than air while the sample beam is used to probe the sample. A comparison between the collected reference beam and the sample beam allows the instrument to make inference about the reflectance or transmittance properties of the sample. The sample beam is incident on the sample at an incidence angle of 7° . BaSO_4 is used as a standard for beam intensity calibration, which has an absolute reflectance of $98.0 \pm 0.5\%$ in the visible regime. All measurements are performed in air and at room temperature.

Similar to reflectance measurements discussed in section 4.7, the measurements reported in this section were also carried out with an Integrating Sphere (IS) of 15 cm diameter. The IS is needed for collecting the diffuse light scattered and reflected from a wide range of angles (see figure 6.27). Since fluorescence is diffused emission, the use of IS is important.

Two limitations of this technique are that the measurements are at RT not liquid argon temperature (approx. 85 K) and the excitation wavelength is not 128 nm. Despite the limitations, this technique is important since it is much faster compared to the cryogenic measurements discussed in the previous section. With the spectrophotometer, we were able to complete approximately 40 measurements in a day, whereas we can only complete 2 measurements in a week with ArGSet. Therefore, for quality assessment, the majority of the samples will be analysed with the spectrophotometer. Only a smaller subset of these samples will be analysed at the cryogenic temperature with ArGSet.

The figure 6.28 shows the reflectance spectra for different samples of PEN. Note that since materials such as PEN produces fluorescence at UV wavelengths, the reflectance measurements increases with decreasing wavelength starting at approximately 235 nm. The spectra shown here includes both the reflected component and the fluorescence component. At short wavelengths, the emitted power is dominated by fluorescence. The ratio of photons absorbed to photons emitted through fluorescence

(a) Exterior of the UV-3600 spectrophotometer. An integrating sphere has been attached to the spectrophotometer.

(b) The image shows a sample attached to the sample holder at the integrating sphere port.

Figure 6.27: Shimadzu UV-3600 spectrophotometer

is called fluorescence quantum yield or fluorescence yield. Therefore, the measurement at 190 nm are a measure of combined fluorescence yield and reflectance of the sample.

The way the measurements were performed for this study is by keeping the PEN samples in front of the sample beam. The PEN samples were not backed with a substrate. Therefore, a fraction of the light transmitted through the PEN samples gets reflected by the door of IS and passes through the PEN sample again and this is registered by the photosensor as well. The blue curve in fig 6.28 shows that the absorber strip attached to the door of the IS (6.27b) is not a good absorber and, in fact, reflects approximately 20% light back into the IS in the absence of a sample. The absence of a reflecting substrate also results in a reduced specular reflectance component in the total emission from the sample.

6.6.2 PEN samples

The PEN variants catalogued in the table 6.3 will be analysed with the spectrophotometer. Furthermore, to probe the WLSE along the axial length of the PEN roll for DarkSide-20k veto (Q51 25 μm), I divide the PEN roll into three equal sections, i.e., sections I, II, III, along the axis (see figure 6.1) and extract samples from them. The samples A, B, and C are respectively taken from sections I, II, and III (see table 6.4).

Table 6.3: Catalogue of PEN samples

Product Variant	Thickness (μm)	Experiment	Year of Procurement	Note
Teonex Q51	25	2PAC	2020	Bought from Teijin Films (via Inabata)
Teonex Q51	25	DS-20k veto	2023	Bought from Toyobo. PEN roll.
Teonex Q51	50	-	2020	Test sample from Teijin Films (via Inabata)
Teonex Q53	25	DWArF	2022	Bought from Goodfellow

Figure 6.28: Average reflectance + fluorescence yield for various PEN samples types.

6.6.3 Welch's t-test

Using Welch's t-test [136, 137], I can establish whether the mean fluorescence yields are consistent across different PEN samples. Welch's t-test was selected for this study, since it remains a valid statistical test even if the number of measurements and variances are unequal for the PEN samples.

First, I calculate the t-statistic using the following expression:

$$t_{stat} = \frac{(\bar{x}_A - \bar{x}_B) - (\mu_A - \mu_B)}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{s_A}{n_A}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{s_B}{n_B}\right)^2}} \quad (6.9)$$

Where, \bar{x}_A and s_A are the estimated mean and standard deviation of all the measurements performed on sample A while μ_A is the hypothesized true mean of the sample A. n_A is the number of measurements performed on sample A.

For the null hypothesis, $\mu_A = \mu_B$,

$$t_{stat} = \frac{(\bar{x}_A - \bar{x}_B)}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{s_A}{n_A}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{s_B}{n_B}\right)^2}} \quad (6.10)$$

Then, I calculate the degrees of freedom for Welch's t-test:

$$df = \frac{\left(\frac{s_A^2}{n_A} + \frac{s_B^2}{n_B}\right)}{\frac{\left(\frac{s_A^2}{n_A}\right)^2}{n_A - 1} + \frac{\left(\frac{s_B^2}{n_B}\right)^2}{n_B - 1}} \quad (6.11)$$

For a chosen confidence level and the computed value of df, I can use the two-tailed test to comment on the measured means.

6.6.4 Consistency between DarkSide and 2PAC PEN

The scatter plot in the figure 6.29 shows the combined intensity of reflected and fluorescence component compared to reference beam at 190 nm for various PEN samples.

Figure 6.29: Reflectance + fluorescence yield at 190 nm for various PEN samples. The B and B-2 samples are both extracted from the same section of the roll. The difference between the two is the orientation of the PEN sample, in one case the top surface is used for measurement whereas in the other bottom surface is used for the measurement.

Table 6.4: Reflectances of all samples. All quantities are expressed in percentage.

Sample	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Standard Error of the Mean (s/\sqrt{n})
A	118.63	5.84	1.51
B + B-2	121.18	3.04	0.96
C	117.41	3.86	1.00
A + B + B-2 + C	119.01	4.86	0.82
2PAC	114.08	1.61	0.42

For the combined set of measurements on samples A, B, B-2, and C, the t-statistic is calculated from the table 6.4 using the equation 6.10 is 5.35. The degrees of freedom calculated using the equation 6.11 are 30.84. For 95% confidence level and $df=30.84$, the critical statistic for two-tailed t-test turns out to be 2.04. Since the t-statistic for our measurements does not lie in the interval -2.04 to 2.04, I can reject the null hypothesis at the chosen confidence level.

Hence, DarkSide PEN samples do not exhibit mean fluorescence yield consistent with PEN variant used in 2PAC at 95% confidence level.

Figure 6.30: histogram for all DarkSide samples, i.e, A, B, B-2, and C at 190 nm. The sample mean and standard deviation found from this histogram were not used in for constructing table 6.4, still the values are close.

6.6.5 Consistency of top and bottom surface of the DS-20k PEN sheets

The PEN sheets have been observed to exhibit different WLSE on each side of the sheet. Therefore, I will try to comment on the consistency of the top and bottom surfaces of the PEN sheet under investigation.

To clarify what the top and bottom surface are: imagine the PEN sheet wrapped around a cylindrical support structure. The sheet has two surfaces, one whose normal vector faces away from this cylinder, I call this the top surface and another surface whose surface normal goes towards the cylinder, I call it the bottom surface.

Table 6.5: Comparison between top and bottom surfaces. All quantities are expressed in percentages.

Surface type	Mean (\bar{x})	Error in mean	Standard Deviation (s)	Standard Error of the Mean (s/\sqrt{n})
Top	117.65	7.19	6.46	2.28
Bottom	121.49	2.79	4.59	1.53

The t-statistic calculated from the table 6.5 using the equation 6.10 is 1.39. The degrees of freedom calculated using the equation 6.11 are 12.49. For 95% confidence level and $df=12.49$, the critical statistic for two-tailed t-test turns out to be 2.17. Since the t-statistic for our measurements lies in the interval -2.17 to 2.17, I fail to reject the null hypothesis at the chosen confidence level.

Hence, the top and the bottom samples exhibit consistent fluorescence yield at 95% confidence level.

6.6.6 Consistency of centre of the roll with the edges

Table 6.6: Comparison between edge and centre samples. All quantities are expressed in percentages.

Sample location	Mean (\bar{x})	Error in mean	Standard Deviation (s)	Standard Error of the Mean (s/\sqrt{n})
Edges	118.05	1.32	5.41	1.37
Centre	121.18	1.14	3.28	1.04

The t-statistic calculated from the table 6.6 using the equation 6.10 is 1.82. The df calculated using the equation 6.11 is 31.68. For 95% confidence level and $df=31.68$, the critical statistic for two-tailed t-test turns out to be 2.04. Since the t-statistic for our measurements lies in the interval -2.04 to 2.04, I fail to reject the null hypothesis at the chosen confidence level.

Hence, the edge and the centre samples exhibit consistent fluorescence yield at 95% confidence level.

(a) histogram for all top surface reflectances

(b) histogram for all bottom surface reflectances

Figure 6.31: Comparison between the top and the bottom surfaces

(a) histogram for all DarkSide edge samples, i.e., A and C at 190 nm

(b) histogram for DarkSide centre samples, i.e., B and B-2 at 190 nm

Figure 6.32: Comparison between edges and centre reflectance at 190 nm

In summary, all DarkSide-20k PEN samples have consistent fluorescence yield. The top and the bottom surfaces also exhibit statistically consistent fluorescence yield. The fluorescence yield of 2PAC sample is not consistent with DarkSide-20k samples, with the DarkSide-20k samples yielding 4% more light. As the decision of the collaboration to use PEN was based on the 2PAC result, the yield of the production grade PEN for DarkSide-20k veto marginally exceeds the expectations, and is by a safe margin above the minimum specification of 30% WLSE of TPB.

6.7 Summary

Cryogenically stable wavelength shifters are essential for efficiently detecting scintillation photons in liquid argon radiation detectors. However, for large scintillator volumes of the order of 100 m², the use of the most popular wavelength shifter, Tetraphenyl Butadiene (TPB), becomes impractical due to the high energy and labour costs associated with its physical vapour deposition on the detector surface. Polyethylene Naphthalate (PEN) has been proposed as a scalable alternative to TPB, as it is available in the form of large polymeric sheets. The neutron veto of the DarkSide-20k detector will utilize nearly 200 m² of PEN sheets. Findings from several studies suggest significant variability in the wavelength shifting efficiency of PEN across different production batches. Therefore, rigorous quality control is essential.

The gaseous Argon Gas Setup (ArGSet) has demonstrated its effectiveness in quantifying fluorescence from wavelength shifters at cryogenic temperatures. Using gaseous argon greatly simplifies and accelerates the process of fluorescence measurement without compromising accuracy. The setup has been thoroughly evaluated, and several issues were identified and subsequently resolved. Operational protocols were developed to avoid electronic interference from temperature sensor and other components. The setup has proven capable of measuring sPE charges with an acceptable SNR, making it suitable for the quality assessment campaign.

Intermittent noise was handled with the implementation of event selection cuts. The thermal stability of setup was studied and found to be stable for around 10 hours. It was also demonstrated that argon purity remains constant throughout the measurement, indicating no significant out gassing.

Furthermore, asymmetry between the two SiPM signals was observed to vary between measurements, potentially due to inconsistent argon density levels. These fluctuations affect the location of energy deposition, resulting in different amounts of scintillation light reaching the wavelength shifter sample. To address this, a pressure gauge will be installed to accurately monitor the gas pressure. This enhancement is expected to improve the control of systematic effects associated with the setup. This work is planned for future development.

Additionally, fluorescence yield measurements of various PEN samples were conducted using the spectrophotometer. The fluorescence yield of PEN sheets procured for the DarkSide-20k veto was found to be statistically consistent along the sheet's length and across both the top and bottom surfaces. However, a similar level of consistency was not observed between the production-batch DarkSide-20k veto PEN

samples and those used in the 2PAC experiment, with the production batch samples performing marginally better, which is good news for the experiment.

This difference could be due to differences in production batches or history of the material, and combined with ageing effects on the 2PAC PEN samples. While the 2PAC samples have been stored in the dark since their delivery 5 years ago, the production date and full history preceding the delivery is unknown. On the contrary, for the production batch of PEN it has been ensured with the supplier that a freshly produced, at most a couple of months old, batch of PEN was provided. Except for the time needed to collect the samples from the roll, the material has been and until the installation time will be stored hermetically sealed in vacuum aluminized cast polypropylene bagging, in order to limit its exposure to radon, oxygen and ambient light.

Ensuring uniform and reliable wavelength shifting efficiency in PEN sheets enhances confidence in the light collection efficiency of the veto detector. This improvement, in turn, increases the reliability of external background vetoing, which is crucial for achieving the desired WIMP search sensitivity with DarkSide-20k.

Chapter 7

Summary and Conclusion

Λ CDM has been exceptionally successful in explaining the formation of spiral galaxies, the formation of large scale structures, and predicted anisotropies in CMB. A crucial component of this model is dark matter, for which WIMPs have been proposed as a viable candidate. Although no credible detection of WIMPs has yet been made, the parameter space for WIMPs is steadily shrinking. To further constrain this space, more sensitive detectors must be developed, which presents several technological challenges. One promising approach for direct WIMP detection is the use of liquid argon as a target material.

This thesis is entirely focused on the scintillation channel in liquid argon detectors for dark matter searches. A WIMP-argon nucleus collision would produce scintillation light in the VUV regime, peaking at approximately 128 nm. The topics covered in this thesis can be broadly classified into two categories: light collection optimization and Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD).

Chapter 1 introduces the problem of dark matter and provides the motivation for the dark matter search. Chapter 2 offers a brief introduction of liquid argon radiation detectors. These chapters provide the foundation for in-depth discussions that follow.

Chapter 3 reports on our efforts to develop a physics-based PSD technique for suppressing the dominant background caused by β decay of ^{39}Ar . This ambitious project aims to replace the prevalent technique, which relies on effective PSD models. I present an overview of the physical processes incorporated into our model, describing the chain of events from the release of a β particle to the generation of a photoelectron on the photocathode of the PMT. Although the model does not achieve full agreement with the complete experimental dataset, we have achieved consistency with a small subset of the data. After identifying and mitigating some mathematical issues in the code and validating the fitter, I have ruled out the most obvious causes of the discrepancy. Several areas for potential refinement in both the model and its implementation have been identified, which should be addressed in future work.

Chapter 4 describes an analytic formalism for quantification of light collection in liquid argon detectors. I demonstrate the usefulness of a Python-based tool, developed from this analytic model, in providing quick estimates of light yield (LY) for liquid argon detectors. The model successfully estimated the LY for a tabletop experiment, and its predictions were cross-verified with Monte Carlo simulations.

Additionally, I present LY estimates for the DarkSide-20k neutron veto and compare them with Monte Carlo simulations. LY estimates for planned liquid argon detectors, such as ARGO and DUNE, are also discussed.

Chapter 5 delves into light collection with wavelength shifters in liquid argon detectors. Particularly, the focus is on the two experimental campaigns in which I participated to characterise PEN wavelength shifters. The first campaign took place at UZH, where we performed measurements on different combinations of PEN wavelength shifter variants available in the market, as well as various reflectors. Based on these measurements, the PEN variant sold under the brand name Teonex Q53 (25 μm) was selected for a month-long measurement campaign at CERN. This campaign demonstrated that a relatively large amount of PEN Q53 consistently provided stable light collection under cryogenic conditions for a continuous period of two weeks.

Chapter 6 presents the latest developments in our efforts to characterise PEN wavelength shifters. As the construction of DarkSide-20k progresses, we have also begun preparing to deliver PEN sheets for use in its veto detector. To this end, we commissioned and calibrated a custom-built setup for quality assessment of these PEN sheets at cryogenic temperatures utilising gas argon scintillation. Previously, noise issues had previously prevented us from calculating the sPE charge, but I developed an algorithm to reject noisy events from the dataset. This enabled me to measure the sPE charge and determine the SNR to be approximately 2, which was deemed acceptable for our purposes. Consequently, we proceeded with the planned measurements of PEN wavelength shifters. I demonstrated that the setup remained thermally stable for approximately 10 hours and that the argon purity did not deteriorate significantly during measurements. First measurement results of the PEN wavelength shifters are also presented. Additionally, I measured the fluorescence yield of PEN samples at room temperature using 190 nm excitation. I verified that the PEN sheets procured for the DarkSide-20k veto detector have consistent fluorescence yield along the axial length of the roll.

Appendix A

Online PSD analysis for DEAP-3600

A.1 Introduction

I developed a Python script for applying PSD in an online analysis framework for DEAP-3600 dark matter detector. The Python script re-implements an existing C++ code used by the DEAP-3600 collaboration. The Python script uses the C++ implementation of the effective model and the routine for fitting the model to the data. The C++ implementation of effective PSD model is described in [138].

This script is based on a common script format for various online analyses. What I mean by Online analysis is that the whole analysis will be done autonomously with little to no human input on an almost real-time basis. I only handled the PSD analysis, other analyses such as PMT calibration are handled by other members of the collaboration. All the scripts are part of autonomous data analysis pipeline auto-DEAP which was planned to run once every week to produce relevant plots so that detector parameters could be monitored while refilling of DEAP-3600. As of writing of this thesis, the refilling is yet to begin. Since there has been no new data collection, I have only been able to create demo plots using existing data.

A.2 Pipeline

The Python script performs the following operations in sequence:

1. Create a 2D histogram from all events. The number of PE is on the x-axis and the y-axis corresponds to one of the PSD parameters, e.g., F_{Prompt} or R_{Prompt} . PE is specified as one of the PE parameters, such as ‘qPE’ or ‘nSC’ etc. The histogram is shown in figure A.1. The parameters to be used are specified in an ASCII config file. Note that qPE represents PE calculated from PMT charge, while the nSC parameter is essentially qPE computed after performing after-pulsing correction using sophisticated algorithms developed by DEAP-3600 collaboration. Similarly, R_{Prompt} is the PSD parameter obtained after performing

after-pulsing correction. These parameters are supposed to be calculated by other modules prior to the PSD processing.

2. Apply all the cuts. A label specific to each cut is displayed on the resultant histogram (see figure [A.2](#)). The cut cheat sheet (figure [A.4](#)) helps to match labels with cut conditions.
3. Create 1D histograms. Each 1D histogram corresponds to a range of values of the PE parameter (see figure [A.3](#)).
4. Perform fits on the 1D histograms. The fitting process is initiated by calling a C++/ROOT macro that is part of DEAP-3600 software suite. The effective PSD model and the fitting algorithm are not implemented in Python module. The PSD fit to 1D histogram is shown in [A.3](#).
5. Save the plots as PDF and ROOT files.

Note: I choose a range of values of the PE parameter for creating the 1D histograms. Larger ranges would produce too many plots and proportionately consume the computing resources. Therefore, an optimal range of values of the charge parameter is needed.

In conclusion, the Python module has demonstrated its capability to perform PSD analysis on DEAP-3600 data by utilising existing tools available within the DEAP-3600 software suite.

Figure A.1: Demo histogram generated by the Python script for online analysis

Figure A.2: All cuts applied for PSD analysis

PhysicsTrigger_OpenData2018_L2

v5.14.0

qPE;
 dtmTrigSrc;
 trigTime;
 numEarlyPulses;
 fmaxpe;
 fmaxnsc;
 pulseindexfirstgar;
 zCut;

livetime: 60186.992 s

Pass Rate: -- Hz

ntp

calcut;
 subeventN;
 eventTime;
 deltat;
 neckVetoN;
 ChargetopringFrac;
 mblikelihoodR;
 rCut;

Fail Rate: -- Hz

Figure A.3: Effective model fit to demo histogram. Note: these fits have not been optimized as there has not been any new data.

Label	Expression
qPE	data.qPE > 0
Calcut	not (data.calcut & 0x31f8)
dtmTrigSrc	not (data.dtmTrigSrc & 0x82)
subeventN	data.subeventN <= 1
trigTime	-99999.9 < data.trigTime < 99999.9
eventTime	2300 < data.eventTime < 2650
numEarlyPulses	data.numEarlyPulses <= 3
deltat	20000 < data.deltat
fmaxpe	data.fmaxpe < 0.4
neckVetoN	data.neckVetoN <= 0
fmaxnsc	data.fmaxnsc < 99.99
ChargeTopringFrac	(data.chargetopring + data.chargesecondring) / data.qPE < 9999.9
pulseindexfirstgar	-999 < data.pulseindexfirstgar
mblikelihoodR	not ((data.mblikelihoodR >= 750) or (data.mblikelihoodZ >= 550))
zCut	zCut.IsInside(promptPE, (tf2Pos.Z() - mbPos.Z()))
rCut	rCut.IsInside(promptPE, (tf2Pos.mbPos).Mag())

Figure A.4: Cheatsheet for matching cut labels with cut conditions.

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